

D8.2: 'Just' transition pathway & intermediate targets

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Table of Contents

Glossary of terms and acronyms used.....	8
Executive Summary.....	9
1. Introduction.....	10
1.1 ZeroW project summary.....	10
1.2 Mapping ZeroW outputs.....	13
1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	16
1.4 Synergies with other Work Packages.....	18
1.4.1 WP1 economic model simulations.....	18
1.4.2 Cooperation with European Commission services & other project/initiatives (WP9)	18
1.4.3 Fostering systemic innovation & building capacity towards near-zero Food Loss and Waste (WP6)	19
2. The transition scenarios (goals and approaches)	20
2.1 Revisiting the three alternative policy pathways (D'haese et al., 2023).....	20
2.2 Overview of the pathways' targets, actions, and approaches (D'haese et al., 2023).....	21
2.2.1 Pathway 1 (P1) - "Green growth": market-drive policy innovation for sustainable FW reduction.....	21
2.2.2 Pathway 2 (P2) – Changing the rules: structural governance shift for near- zero food waste.....	24
2.2.3 Pathway 3 (P3) – Innovation first: teaming up for inclusive FW reduction	26
3. Modelling the impact of the FLW interventions in each policy pathway.....	30
3.1 Partial equilibrium model and MAGNET analysis results	30
3.1.1 Partial equilibrium model - Mandatory targets (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)	30
3.1.2 Partial Equilibrium model - Voluntary targets (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025).....	32
3.1.3 MAGNET analysis (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025).....	33
3.2 Reflection on key insights and findings (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)	36
4. Defining a 'just pathway'.....	41
4.1 Assessing the status quo: actors, vulnerabilities and justice dimensions in the food system	41
4.1.1 Mapping the Food Supply Chain (FSC).....	42

4.1.2 Identifying the vulnerable groups in the status quo	42
4.1.3 Dimensions of justice	45
4.1.4 The digital divide.....	47
4.2 Transformative changes for a just transition.....	47
4.2.1 Reforming the food system and market practices	47
4.2.2 (Gradually) shortening the Food Supply Chain (FSC).....	48
4.2.3 Bridging the digital divide: inclusive innovation.....	49
4.2.4 Incentivising and advancing FLW reduction: monitoring and measurement	50
4.3 Stakeholder engagement and equitable distribution of responsibilities	51
4.3.1 The role of external actors in the transition.....	51
4.3.2 Collaborative approaches to address food system vulnerabilities	52
4.3.3 Applying frameworks for a just transition	53
5. Methodology	55
5.1 Research design and data collection	55
5.2 Combining a quantitative and qualitative approach to set the targets.....	56
6. Setting just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets towards 2050... 59	
6.2 Drawing from the modelling results and stakeholders' roundtables: Setting the targets.....	60
6.3 Towards specific policy recommendations: Integrations with the ZeroW SILLs	
75	
7. Conclusions	86
8. References.....	87
Annex I: Guiding questions for the ZeroW Food Waste roundtables	94
Annex II: List of participants for the ZeroW Food Waste roundtables.....	98
Annex III: List of short-listed external experts and stakeholders contacted by the ZeroW Policy Team for participation in the roundtables.....	99
Annex IV: Internal ZeroW workshop with WP1 and WP6 - Matching exercise between D8.2 and SILLs outcomes	103

List of figures

Figure 1: ZeroW at a glance	10
Figure 2: ZeroW approach	11
Figure 3: WP8 tasks, deliverables, objectives.....	11
Figure 4: WP1 tasks, deliverables, objectives.....	12
Figure 5: Visualisation of the three alternative pathways (D’haese et al., 2023).....	21
Figure 6: Overview of the conceptual framework	41
Figure 7: Overview of the Food Supply Chain (FSC).....	42
Figure 8: Different pathways towards near-zero FLW (D’haese et al., 2023).....	55
Figure 9: Changes in edible FLW rates along the supply chain for different policy pathways (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)	63
Figure 10: Required % change in disposal costs along the supply chain for different policy pathways (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)	64
Figure 11: Changes in the total quantity of FLW for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030 (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)	67
Figure 12: Required % shift of the abatement costs for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030 (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)	68
Figure 13: Change (million tons of CO ₂ -equivalents) in greenhouse gas emissions by source in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050 (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025)	71
Figure 14: Change (million tons of CO ₂ -equivalents) in greenhouse gas emissions by country in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.....	72
Figure 15: Overview of the ZeroW SILLs	75
Figure 16: Overview of the Just Pathway Actions	76

List of tables

Table 1: Glossary of terms and acronyms used	8
Table 2: Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description	15
Table 3: Conceptualisations of the different pathways (D’haese et al., 2023).....	20
Table 4: FW reduction targets in P1 (D’haese et al., 2023).....	22
Table 5: FW reduction targets in P2 (D’haese et al., 2023).....	25
Table 6: FW reduction targets in P3 (D’haese et al., 2023).....	27
Table 7: Final proposal for just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets (2030).....	73

Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
BaU	Business as Usual
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CGE	Computable General Equilibrium
CSA	Community Supported Agriculture
EC	European Commission
EGD	European Union Green Deal
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FAFH	Food consumption Away From Home
FAH	Food consumption At Home
FL	Food Loss
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FSC	Food Supply Chain
FW	Food Waste
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas Emissions
GTAP	Global Trade Analysis
HRI	Hotel Restaurant Institutional
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MS	Member State
MAGNET	Modular Applied GeNeral Equilibrium Tool
NET	NaturEaTown
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
P1	Pathway 1
P2	Pathway 2
P3	Pathway 3
PPPs	Public-Private Partnerships
SD	System Dynamics
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SFSCs	Short Food Supply Chains
SILLs	Systemic Innovation Living Labs
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
TBL	Triple Bottom Line
UN	United Nations
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WUR	Wageningen University and Research

Table 1: Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Executive Summary

This report is the second deliverable released by the ZeroW Policy Team (WP8). It tackles the pressing issue of Food Loss and Waste (FLW) within the European Union (EU) by defining what a **'just pathway'** for FLW reduction looks like. It also **quantifies key challenges, identifies trade-offs and threshold levels beyond which proposed targets may become unrealistic**. The goal is to provide a clear framework and a practical selection of just and achievable targets for 2030 that align with the *Farm-to-Fork Action Plan* and the European Commission (EC) Proposal for EU-level food waste reduction targets. However, the report highlights the complex range of factors and actions that EU policymakers must consider to render these objectives achievable.

This report interprets and analyses the **results of the modelling simulations** for the three alternative transition policy pathways illustrated in D8.1. It combines this analysis with a conceptual framework centred on the just pathway and validates the findings by incorporating valuable insights and feedback from stakeholders, gathered during two working group roundtables.

This analysis leads to a comprehensive discussion of the modelling simulations and the three alternative pathways, setting the stage for the selection and proposal of the intermediate just and realistic FLW reduction targets. These targets represent a **compromise** balancing the need to mitigate some of the negative consequences while still achieving a meaningful reduction and positive impact. Crucially, the report stresses that selecting these targets cannot be decoupled from the urgent need for policymakers to address **their potential unintended consequences and the identified trade-offs**.

Ultimately, the report offers a non-exhaustive **list of 'Just Pathway Actions'**, which are essential for successfully achieving the proposed targets and prompting reflection for policymakers. Drawing from an internal ZeroW workshop, the report also integrates the **ongoing work of the ZeroW SILLs**, illustrating how the innovations they are developing and testing contribute to the realisation of the Just Pathway Actions and the proposed FLW reduction targets. This process lays the foundation for the **development of the EU Policy Briefs** calling for more targeted policy interventions and recommendations.

1. Introduction

This chapter provides a high-level overview of the ZeroW project and more specifically Work Package 8 (WP8) (section 1.1). Section 1.2 maps the ZeroW outputs within T8.2 of WP8. Subsequently, the chapter provides a detailed overview of the deliverable and its structure (section 1.3) while the final section focuses on the various synergies with other WPs that have supported the development process of this deliverable.

1.1 ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste (FLW) by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (OFLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1: ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2: ZeroW approach

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables. Figure 3 shows an overview of the WP8 composition.

Figure 3: WP8 tasks, deliverables, objectives

This report showcases the entire process of T8.2 and the related work that was carried out to define a 'just' transition pathway and indicate a set of feasible intermediate targets. It continues the process started with T8.1 and described in D8.1, as the alternative near-zero FLW pathways have been simulated in the economic models developed by WP1 (see figure 4). The results of these simulations are presented and analysed in this report, further validated by a conceptual framework and insights from stakeholders of the Food Supply Chain (FSC). The outcomes of this report will directly inform the development of short- and medium-term FLW policy recommendations to be produced in T8.3.

Figure 4: WP1 tasks, deliverables, objectives

1.2 Mapping ZeroW outputs

WP8 focuses on providing alternative transition pathways towards near-zero FLW in 2050, indicating a 'just' transition pathway and intermediate targets to get to this situation, and finally providing short- and medium-term policy recommendations for policymakers across the EU. This report is the second deliverable of *WP8 - Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW*. This chapter maps ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D8.2 'Just' transition pathway & intermediate targets</i>	<i>Will report on the process and results of building a 'Just' transition pathway.</i>	<i>All chapters and sections.</i>	<i>This document provides a comprehensive report on the process, activities, and results of building a 'just' transition pathway and setting realistic intermediate targets towards 2050.</i>
TASKS			
<i>T8.2 A 'just' transition pathway and intermediate targets to near-zero FLW by 2050</i>	Developing a 'just' transition pathway requires two conditions to be met: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) the pathway has to be able to reach near-zero FLW by 2050 based on evidence and assumptions that are considered valid; 2) the pathway should allocate in a balanced way the costs, benefits and risks of this transition to all actors involved, 	<i>All chapters and sections.</i>	This document provides a report of the following activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revisiting the alternative policy pathways from D8.1 and providing an overview of their targets (alongside actions and approaches) that were simulated (Chapter 2).

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<p>including the consumers. This will be achieved combining a quantitative and a qualitative approach. The quantitative approach will be provided by T1.3 through the modelling the impact of the FLW interventions included in each alternative transition pathway. The qualitative approach will be provided in this Task, by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) the policy-related ZeroW partners not involved in T1.3; the members of the 3 WGs formulated in T8.1. b) The FLW modelling results will be presented and analysed in round table discussions and the ZeroW project team will enrich them, revise them or ask for modelling iteration before presenting the proposed version to be validated by the WG members. <p>T8.2 will also make sure that the ‘just’ transition pathway is constructed so that it provides a balance between long-term ambition and medium-term action. The medium terms actions will involve:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) setting just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets towards 2050, to meet the requirement of the F2F Action Plan (Proposal for EU-level targets for food waste reduction); 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clustering the main results from the modelling simulations and reflecting on their key insights (Chapter 3). - Formulating a conceptual framework to define a ‘just pathway’ and its several dimensions (Chapter 4). - Setting just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets towards 2050, identifying key trade-offs and actions that need to be considered and addressed for the development of a just pathway (Chapter 6). - Organising working group roundtables for analysing, validating, and gathering feedback on the modelling simulations (Section 5.2).

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
	<p>b) identifying areas where more specific policy interventions will be required in the short and medium term.</p> <p>The first one will be provided by this Task, while the second one by T8.3 that follows. The 'just' transition pathway and the intermediate targets will be widely disseminated and validated through awareness activities, and events with targeted European bodies in the food sector and also in consultation with the relevant EC services.</p>		

Table 2: Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The ZeroW project aims to contribute to the objectives and targets set by the *Farm-to-fork* Strategy (F2F) and the *EU Green Deal* (EGD), to halve the per capita Food Waste (FW) levels (at consumer and retail stages) by 2030. By the end of the project in 2025, we collectively aim to reduce FW by 20% at retail and by 25% at consumer level through our Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs); whilst on the medium-term (i.e. 2030) we aim to contribute to the 50% reduction of per capita FW at retail and consumer levels and, on the long-term (i.e. 2050.), we aim to reach a near-zero FW per capita.

Deliverable D8.1 defined the state-of-play of FLW in the European Union (EU) and devised a trend pathway of FW reduction, using a systemic approach to address the problem throughout the supply chain. We defined and developed three alternative, forward-looking distinct pathways. These implement innovative and sustainable FW practices to minimise or eliminate their generation throughout the FSC, with different levels of change concerning policymaking, innovation and consumer behaviour. Through Working Groups (WGs) and interviews, we collaborated with FSC stakeholders, providing a better understanding of all the dynamics around FW generation and reduction in the EU.

In this report, we aim to continue this process by building on the three transition scenarios outlined and reflecting on the simulations made using quantitative analysis within WP1 (T1.3). The results were presented and analysed in roundtable discussions with stakeholders from across the FSC, providing valuable feedback on their feasibility and potential implications. This report integrates this process with a non-exhaustive literature review on the definition and undertaking of a 'just pathway' for FLW reduction, which is further enriched by discussions among WP8 partners and written feedback from external stakeholders. Ultimately, we attempt to identify just and realistic intermediate targets in line with a just pathway towards near-zero FLW in 2050, providing potential integrations with the interventions being developed in the ZeroW SILLs.

This deliverable is constructed in 7 key chapters:

- In the **first chapter**, we describe the context of the present report (sections 1.1, 1.2, 1.3) and map the synergies between the work of the ZeroW Policy team (WP8) and other WPs (section 1.4), with WP1 in the framework of the modelling (or quantitative analysis) simulations.
- In the **second chapter**, we briefly represent and revisit the three alternative policy pathways identified in D8.1 (section 2.1), providing a concise overview of their main targets, actions, and approaches (section 2.2), which informed the modelling simulations directly.

- In the **third chapter**, we present the analysis and results of the modelling simulations of the three alternative pathways carried out by WP1 (led by the Wageningen University), focusing and reflecting on their key insights and findings.
- In the **fourth chapter**, we aim to define a theoretical, conceptual framework centred around the definition of a 'just pathway' and its objectives. We provide a state of play that starts with assessing the status quo of the food system and its vulnerabilities (section 4.2.1). Importantly, it explores the transformative changes needed to support a just pathway (section 4.2.2), while emphasising stakeholder engagement and equitable distribution of responsibilities across the value chain (section 4.2.3).
- In the **fifth chapter**, we delineate the methodological considerations of the deliverable regarding the scope of our quantitative (WP1) and qualitative (WP8) analysis, further validating it through stakeholder consultation processes (roundtable WGs and written questionnaires).
- In the **sixth chapter**, we delineate the entire process combining these two approaches. Using the requirements of the *F2F Plan* (section 6.1) as a benchmark, we analyse the suggested targets from each alternative policy pathway and the considerations from the modelling results, assessing how just and feasible they are and integrating them with our conceptual framework and with the feedback from the stakeholders who participated in the roundtables. We choose and set balanced and indicative targets (section 6.2) that emerged from our analysis as the most 'just' and 'realistic'. This chapter concludes by highlighting key 'Just Pathway Actions' and trade-offs to consider, and it incorporates the results of a matching exercise from an internal ZeroW workshop. This exercise explored potential integrations with the ZeroW SILLs, examining how they contribute to achieving the just pathway and targets, along with the associated challenges. This last section lays the foundation for the work of the next task T8.3, focused on identifying specific policy interventions. Our conclusions regarding the main findings and considerations of our analysis are shared in a concise **seventh and final chapter**.

Appendixes at the end of the report indicate:

- Guiding questions for the ZeroW Food Waste roundtables;
- The list of participants for the roundtables;
- The list of short-listed external experts and stakeholders contacted by the ZeroW Policy Team for participation in the roundtables;
- Internal ZeroW workshop with WP1 and WP6 - Matching exercise between D8.2 and SILLs outcomes.

1.4 Synergies with other Work Packages

This section highlights the complex interaction between WP8 – *Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW* and the broader activities within the ZeroW project, highlighting their collaborative synergy, strategic methodologies, and aligned pursuit of a shared objective: defining a ‘just’ transition pathway to near-zero FLW.

1.4.1 WP1 economic model simulations

Building on the synergies and interactions described in our Deliverable D8.1, this report focuses on the economic model simulations carried out by WP1 in T1.3. These simulations of the alternative policy pathways presented in D8.1 informed the modelling work, which was further refined through regular communication and ad-hoc meetings between WP1 and WP8. This tight collaboration continued through the course of T8.2, allowing us to indicate what a ‘just transition’ pathway would be.

1.4.2 Cooperation with European Commission services & other project/initiatives (WP9)

WP8 and WP9 regularly liaise with EU institutions and other projects. WP9 provides WP8 with valuable updates, event notifications, and inquiries from related Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects taking part in the following networks/platforms:

- [Cooperation and Collaboration Network \(CCN\)](#) clustering with over 30 other projects and initiatives in the field of FLW;
- The [FOOD2030](#) Project collaboration network aimed at joining forces across projects, partnerships and networks working on shifting the food system to become more fair, healthy and sustainable.
- The [Green Deal Support Office \(GD-SO\)](#) that coordinates the research and innovation projects funded under the Green Deal Call and their participation in the Food WG.

In November 2023, ZeroW and SISTERS published a [joint Statement](#) on Food Waste Reduction, endorsed by 9 projects¹. We called for an ambitious set of reduction targets for Member States (MSs) and policy consistency across the EU. The statement was used for advocacy and dissemination activities and praised by the GDSO. Building on this effort, together with WP9, the WP8 Leader (SAFE) took part in key events to collaborate with fellow projects and share expertise, challenges, and solutions:

¹ Agro2Circular, ClieNFarms, ENOUGH, PestNu, SchoolFood4Change, EcoeFISHient, NeoGIANT, WASTELESS, and FOLLOU.

- **June 17-18, 2024:** Webinar *“Current Developments in Food Loss & Waste Reduction”* hosted by FOLOU and WASTELESS. ZeroW Policy Lead gave a presentation on:
 - Overview of EU legislative progress and challenges in FLW reduction.
 - Insights from WP8 policy work, including identifying vulnerable groups in the just transition.
- **June 25, 2024:** GDSO workshop *“Challenges in Stakeholder Inclusion in the Food Sector”*, organised by EcoeFISHent, PestNu, and SISTERS projects.
 - Key highlights: addressed stakeholder scepticism and developed recommendations. Featured ‘impulse talks,’ incl. input from DG Research & Innovation.
- **Participation in the International Conference** *“Towards Halving Food Waste in Europe”* on June 18, 2024, in Veghel (NL) to present together with other GDSO projects a unified policy stance and recommendations for FLW reduction.

1.4.3 Fostering systemic innovation & building capacity towards near-zero Food Loss and Waste (WP6)

WP6 partners (ILVO) invited the WP8 Leader (SAFE) to participate in a study visit on FW and Redistribution in Catalonia, Spain. The trip consisted of field visits to a processing company (Indulleida) producing orange juice for food banks using unsold fruit taken out of the market; a company selling boxes with imperfect fruits and vegetables (Talkualfoods); Foodbank Barcelona; the production site of Espigoladores. The visits offered valuable insights into an operational context of processing companies, food waste-reducing start-ups, and food banks in Barcelona, as well as their collaboration with the Foodback programme. The trip included a policy workshop that explored the differences in regulatory and policy measures for food redistribution between Spain and Belgium, featuring representatives from the Catalanian government and the FOLOU project.

2. The transition scenarios (goals and approaches)

In this second chapter, we revisit and briefly describe the three policy scenarios identified in D8.1 (section 2.1), highlighting their respective targets that have been simulated in the economic models by WP1. Additionally, we discuss the actions, principles, and approaches that define each scenario (section 2.3).

2.1 Revisiting the three alternative policy pathways (D’haese et al., 2023)

Three distinct approaches emerge from a literature review on FLW management, sustainability innovation, and consumer behaviours, complemented by insights from discussions with external stakeholders in past WG meetings and interviews conducted. In designing these scenarios, a comprehensive list of barriers and opportunities at each stage of the FSC was carefully considered. This list can be found in section 2.2.2 of D8.1. These approaches signal potential directions for shaping the future of EU policymaking on FLW (D’haese et al., 2023).

Approach with regards to...	Pathway 1	Pathway 2	Pathway 3
Policies	<i>Pragmatic</i>	<i>Vertical</i>	<i>Horizontal</i>
Innovation	<i>Green growth</i>	<i>“Sustainability first”</i>	<i>Solutionism</i>
Consumer behaviour	<i>Semi-interventionism</i>	<i>Dirigisme</i>	<i>Market-driven</i>

Table 3: Conceptualisations of the different pathways (D’haese et al., 2023)

These alternative pathways have intentionally been described in contrasting (or even polarised) terms. These are not predictions, recommendations nor the only options available to future actors, innovators and policymakers in the food system. Instead, they offer a framework for scenario modelling that was used as a starting point for discussion about what a fair transition pathway could look like, informing the conceptual framework in Chapter 4.

Figure 5: Visualisation of the three alternative pathways (D'haese et al., 2023)

2.2 Overview of the pathways' targets, actions, and approaches (D'haese et al., 2023)

2.2.1 Pathway 1 (P1) - "Green growth": market-drive policy innovation for sustainable FW reduction

This first pathway takes a pragmatic and market-driven approach to FLW reduction, recognising the slow progress toward Sustainable Development Goal 12.3 (SDG). It sets **legally binding targets alongside ambitious voluntary agreements** at different stages of the FSC, with percentage-based reduction goals set from a 2020-2022 baseline average to 2032 for processing, manufacturing, retail, and consumption. The aim is to improve accountability, data collection, refine FW definitions, and support measurement of FW at the redistribution level. The proposal assumes continued coordination in FLW management, food safety reviews, and support for shorter supply chains. This pathway embraces a green growth model, where economic expansion aligns with environmental and social objectives. Innovation is encouraged through public investment in research and development, the promotion of social enterprises, and regulatory measures addressing unfair trade practices. Consumer behaviour interventions include awareness campaigns, behavioural nudging, improved labelling, and technological innovations like smart fridges and reformed date-marking systems. This approach assumes that while policy frameworks and incentives will steer progress, market forces will ultimately drive FLW reduction.

This scenario builds on recent legislative positions, adjusted for future challenges with input from stakeholders. The European Commission (EC) and the Joint Research Centre’s (JRC) review of the Waste Framework Directive (WFD) highlight slow progress toward SDG 12.3 (Stroodsnijder et al., 2023). Only a few leading MS are on track for significant progress by 2030. While many countries have some local actions, coordinated national strategies or roadmaps remain rare, and existing plans often lack concrete targets and indicators. A pragmatic option would be to use this assessment as a ‘reality-checked’ starting point, adjusting FW reduction objectives to fit the current situation while aiming for ambitious reductions.

The EC emphasises the need for clear targets, robust measurement mechanisms, and issues management. This approach includes setting specific reduction targets, tracking FW to identify hotspots and monitoring progress. This scenario promotes **ambitious voluntary targets** (Goossens et al., 2019) - **50% reduction in retail and consumption**, (aligned with SDG 12.3) and **25% in manufacturing/processing** (in line with FAO, 2023) - to stimulate private sector actions, especially in retail, hospitality and food services. However, given limited progress in some MS due to the lack of strategic plans, P1 combines voluntary agreements with legally binding targets for all stages of the FSC. Processing and manufacturing are seen as ‘low-hanging fruits’ due to economic incentives for FW reduction (European Commission, 2023a):

Food waste reduction target on:	Mandatory FW reduction target	Voluntary FW reduction target
Primary production	n/a	n/a
Processing and manufacturing	10% (absolute amounts in mass units)	25% (absolute amounts in mass units)
Retail	30% (per capita)	50% (per capita)
Consumption	30% (per capita)	50% (per capita)

Table 4: FW reduction targets in P1 (D’haese et al., 2023)

Target levels are based on the EC proposal to revise the WFD. Primary production is excluded, as farmers argue they only produce FW when unavoidable due to factors beyond their control (e.g., last-minute cancellation of orders from buyers). Retail and consumption stages are separated to avoid unfairly blaming retailers for slow progress on household FW. However, this may blur the line between retail and consumption FW, necessitating a review of FW definitions to clarify responsibilities for reducing waste. P1 uses the 2020-2022 average as a baseline, acknowledging the

impact of COVID-19 and geopolitical events on FW production across all stages. The **target year** is set for **2032**, allowing two years for the implementation of the Directive, as stakeholders believe the 2030 SDG 12.3 target may be premature.

Adjusting FW definitions and increasing public support for measurement at the food redistribution level is crucial, following the EU's 2019 framework for measuring FW but proposing definitions for 'avoidable' and 'unavoidable' FW, to distinguish between edible wasted food (e.g. 'ugly' fruits discarded by retailers) and inedible waste (e.g. household chicken bones). Food Loss (FL) is excluded, as farming stakeholders see it as unrealistic due to limited resources.

Innovation is leveraged to create economic value while reducing environmental impact, following the "green growth" model (OECD, 2018). It focuses on sustainable development through waste reduction, boosting productivity, creating demand for green goods, strengthening finances via green taxes, and reducing risks from resource scarcity or environmental damage. Following this model implies a set of key considerations:

- **Identifying best practices:** Developing databases for effective FLW reduction, leveraging projects like CHORIZO and networks like the EU FLW Prevention Hub.
- **Growth of social & environmental enterprises:** Encouraging businesses focused on FW reduction and redistribution (e.g., Too Good To Go, Phenix, Happy Hours Market).
- **Addressing unfair trading practices:** Defining 'avoidable' vs. 'unavoidable' FW, with voluntary commitments tackling avoidable FW and public intervention managing unavoidable waste.
- **Market-driven, government-supported strategy:** The EU adopts a limited interventionist role, relying on public investments in innovation and research while letting market forces drive FW reduction.
- **Consumer-focused measures:**
 - Awareness campaigns, education in schools/workplaces, improved date-marking, and food donation initiatives. Importantly, a JRC author participating in the ZeroW Consumer Behaviour WG of T8.1 indicated that awareness-raising campaigns alone are insufficient and must be complemented by additional innovation and policy nudges.
 - Policy nudges may include smaller package sizes, better packaging, labelling improvements, smart fridges/kitchens, and FW calculators to promote sustainable consumer habits.

2.2.2 Pathway 2 (P2) – Changing the rules: structural governance shift for near-zero food waste

In contrast, the second pathway adopts a stricter, top-down governance approach that includes mandatory reporting mechanisms and penalties for non-compliance. **It mandates a uniform 50% reduction in FW by 2030** across all sectors of the FSC, from primary production to consumption, relying less on voluntary agreements. This scenario calls for improved data collection, Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), and sustainability-driven innovation. P2 also envisions greater state intervention to influence consumer behaviour through awareness-raising, nudging strategies, training, and social influences. Businesses must adopt sustainable practices or face fines, creating a shift toward FW reduction. This pathway sets a long-term goal of near-zero FW by 2050, supported by strict regulations and incentives to drive business change.

The objective is to implement a vertical policy integration approach, where top-level decision makers (like the EU) set FW reduction goals and require both governments and private companies to include these goals into their policies. Thus, mandatory reporting would ensure everyone follows through, with penalties for those who do not comply (Giessen, 2011). The advantage of this system is that it creates a unified strategy that can target different areas like environment, energy, and trade policies at once. This could make policies more effective in reducing FW and help overcome common challenges, especially in cases where previous commitments have not been fully implemented. Since progress towards SDG 12.3 on FW has been slow, partly due to the fragmented distribution of responsibilities for waste management across EU and national levels, and local authorities (Schleyer et al., 2015), P2 proposes a more radical approach, treating FW reduction as a top societal priority, leading to strong, legally binding commitments exceeding current measures.

Mandatory reduction targets are applied **across all stages** of the FSC, with a limited role of voluntary agreements. Compared to the first pathway, P2 proposes a more comprehensive approach to FLW reduction, prioritising the alignment with the SDG 12.3 deadline. This broader target includes all stages of food production, from primary production to retail, as recommended by [Champions 12.3](#), a coalition advocating for a 50% reduction in all FLW from *farm-to-fork*, including 'food losses'. This approach reflects the urgency of reducing the high levels of FLW and addresses the slow progress made. FW reduction targets are set uniformly at 50% by 2030. The scenario assumes a shift in the FW definition to align with the [FUSIONS definitional framework](#), which includes food losses at the primary production level. **No separate targets** are set for retail versus consumption stages, reflecting the EC WFD revision

and acknowledging the challenges in influencing consumption behaviours, which depend on broader societal and contextual factors (Luchs et al., 2015).

Food waste reduction target on:	Mandatory 2030 FW reduction target	Voluntary 2030 FW reduction target	Mandatory 2050 FW reduction targets
Primary production	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)	For higher target levels	"Near-100%" (absolute amounts in mass units)
Processing and manufacturing	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)		"Near-100%" (absolute amounts in mass units)
Retail & consumption	50% (per capita)		"Near-100%" (absolute amounts in mass units)

Table 5: FW reduction targets in P2 (D'haese et al., 2023)

A civil society participant in the ZeroW Policy WG in T8.1 noted that the impact of voluntary agreements on FW reduction is often overstated. For instance, despite Norway's 2015 agreement with over hundred companies (covering 55% of its market by trade volume) to report FW levels annually and aiming for a 50% reduction by 2030, only a 9,5% reduction was achieved by 2020 (One Planet Network, 2023; Szulecka and Strøm-Andersen, 2021). Consequently, this scenario gives a limited role to voluntary agreements, leveraging them to encourage progress beyond mandatory targets and recognise early adopters. To support the ZeroW project goal of nearly-zero FW by 2050, P2 sets **long-term FW reduction target of close to 100% by 2050**, signalling a strong commitment, and pushes policymakers to devise sustainable, integrated solutions to meet both short- and long-term goals. This scenario aligns with the first mandatory EU-wide FW measurement reported in 2020. The **target year** is **2030**. Achieving these objectives requires a set of key considerations:

- **Updated measurement framework:** FLW definitions and measurement methods will improve and align with the FUSIONS framework, capturing waste across the entire F2F chain, including primary production losses (e.g., waste left in fields, post-harvest losses).
- **Exclusion of pre-harvest waste:** Pre-harvest FW remains outside measurement targets.

- **Stronger policy measures:** To address unavoidable FLW, policies will rebalance power dynamics among FSC actors.
- **Mandatory reporting:** Companies will be legally required to publicly report FLW levels to enhance data accuracy and policy effectiveness.
- **Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR):** Private sector actors will be held accountable for their FW generation and will face penalties if they do not comply with the legally binding targets.

The general approach is **“sustainability first”**: the scenario envisions businesses prioritising sustainability over profit, integrating waste reduction into commercialisation. This also means prioritising surplus redistribution and reinvesting profits from FW reduction innovations into further FW reduction. The underlying assumption is that public and private funding will continuously improve infrastructure for food redistribution. Unlike the previous market-driven model, this scenario relies on government planning and regulation to drive behavioural change, with MS collaborating to centrally manage FW reduction efforts. Price controls and labour market policies would mitigate the negative impacts of FW reduction on households, while adopting an integrated consumer strategy based on:

- awareness campaigns and education programmes;
- in-store measures (e.g., waste-conscious shopping incentives);
- strict business accountability via penalties.

Thus, sustainability would be embedded in food systems through financial incentives, regulations, and education, ensuring that FW reduction becomes the societal norm.

2.2.3 Pathway 3 (P3) – Innovation first: teaming up for inclusive FW reduction

Lastly, the third pathway presents a **more flexible, bottom-up approach** that relies largely on voluntary agreements and collaboration between public authorities, consumers, FSC business actors, and research communities, emphasising the need for inclusive, ad hoc solutions while considering diverse stakeholder interests. This scenario integrates FW reduction objectives into existing policies, proposing ambitious voluntary agreements for FSC actors based on a market-driven framework. P3 embraces a solutionist approach, focusing on innovation as a key driver for FW reduction through technology integration. Additionally, the scenario underscores consumer education and awareness as pivotal, emphasising the role of soft power, economic incentives, and education programs in influencing sustainable behaviours and reducing FW in food systems.

This approach fosters stakeholder cooperation to co-create tailored, bottom-up solutions for ongoing challenges, respecting the limitations, concerns, and interests of each group. The integration of EU policy has been widely explored

(Mahoney, 2008), particularly focusing on the effects of involving different actors, such as FSC operators, in more horizontal governance structures. While stakeholder engagement fosters collaboration, the potential for conflicting priorities underscores the need for balanced, inclusive governance to avoid sidelining essential perspectives in favour of dominant voices. P3 envisions embedding FW reduction objectives directly into sectoral policies, like the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and Fisheries Policies (CFP), aligning them with environmental and societal priorities. Voluntary agreements among FSC actors would be carefully monitored and evaluated according to their efficiency, effectiveness and equity, even though their empirical evaluation proved being challenging (Cabugueira, 2001; Jiménez, 2007). Unlike P1, P3 proposes achieving ambitious FW reduction goals through strong cooperation among FSC actors, supported by flexible legal frameworks.

P3 proposes a **50% FW reduction target by 2030 for retail and consumption (in line with SDG 12.3) and processing and manufacturing** (Champions 12.3 interpretation). It relies primarily on voluntary agreements between public authorities and the private sector guided by roadmaps and performance indicators. Legally binding measures are kept minimal, especially in areas not covered by SDG 12.3 or lacking reliable FLW data such as primary production, processing and manufacturing. **A mandatory 15% reduction target** serves as a baseline, encouraging higher ambitions and support from FSC actors. All targets are set as percentage changes from a 2020–2022 baseline, with a target year of 2030. The goal is a 100% reduction by 2050 (ZeroW objective).

Food waste reduction target on:	2030 Mandatory FW reduction target	2030 Voluntary FW reduction target	2050 Voluntary FW reduction target
Primary production	n/a	10% (absolute amounts in mass units)	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)
Processing and manufacturing	n/a	50% (absolute amounts in mass units)	100% (absolute amounts in mass units)
Retail and consumption	15% (per capita)	50% (per capita)	100% (per capita)

Table 6: FW reduction targets in P3 (D'haese et al., 2023)

While no 2030 target is set for primary production due to the lack of a measurement framework, this scenario aims to include it in the 2050 targets once standards are established (Joensuu et al., 2020). As primary production accounted for only 9% of total EU FW in 2021 (Eurostat, 2021), substantial reduction across all FSC stages could lead to a near-zero FW situation by 2050.

A fundamental consideration in this scenario is the necessary improvement of data collection and sources, as well as adjusting current FW definitions: P3 seeks to improve FW measurements across the FSC, starting with primary production by refining the existing EU harmonised framework²³. It aims to clarify FW definitions, distinguishing between 'avoidable' and 'unavoidable' FW, positioning food recovery as a business opportunity and enhance data quality. P3 does not mandate FL measurement due to resources, time, and capacity within the primary sector. However, it is assumed that voluntary measurement efforts may be feasible in the future with technological advancements.

This pathway also incorporates the assumptions outlined in P1 and proposes several mechanisms for FW reduction:

- **Introduction of market-driven incentives**, such as tax credits, grants, or other financial benefits, to encourage businesses to adopt FW reduction practices.
- **(Public-)Private collaboration** to develop and implement FW reduction initiatives aligned with market interests. Collaborative platforms or industry fora are anticipated to facilitate the sharing of best practices, challenges, and innovations in FW reduction.
- **Market-driven public-private certification programs** to recognise businesses that implement FW reduction measures. Such certifications can serve as a competitive advantage, motivating other companies to adopt sustainable practices.
- **Dynamic regulatory framework** that evolves in response to market conditions and technological advancements while adhering to FW reduction principles.

P3 emphasises flexibility in implementing FW reduction measures, recognising the diversity among businesses. Public authorities would tailor recommendations to

² European Union. *Commission Delegated Decision (EU) 2019/1597 of 3 May 2019 Supplementing Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as Regards a Common Methodology and Minimum Quality Requirements for the Uniform Measurement of Levels of Food Waste*. Official Journal of the European Union, 2019, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/del/2019/1597/oj>.

³ European Union. *Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2019/2000 of 28 November 2019 Laying Down a Methodology for Reporting of Food Waste Levels and Setting out the Format for Member States' Reports in Accordance with Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council*. Official Journal of the European Union, 2019, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/impl/2019/2000/oj>.

suit different sectors, business sizes, and regional needs, enhancing alignment with market-driven principles, fostering innovation, competition, and sustainability. Fundamentally, this scenario prioritises rapid, tech-driven solutions and innovations to address the complex issue of FLW, highlighting entrepreneurship and the need for scalable innovations. Similar to P1, its general approach is market-driven, using economic incentives, education, and awareness programmes to shape consumer behaviour. For instance, it envisions a crucial role for smart purchasing, proper storage, and responsible disposal for FLW reduction, with businesses leading change through improved date labelling, packaging sizes, and pricing strategies. Nudging strategies are also envisioned as private sector-led, allowing businesses to tailor solutions effectively to consumer preferences.

3. Modelling the impact of the FLW interventions in each policy pathway

In this chapter, we present and cluster the key results from the Partial equilibrium modelling and the Modular Applied General Equilibrium tool (MAGNET) analysis (section 3.1), which are further detailed in Deliverable D1.3. Subsequently, we interpret and reflect on the main insights and findings (section 3.2). The results of these simulations provide inputs and a framework for the selection of just, realistic, and coherent reduction targets and definition of a 'just pathway', in combination with the literature review and the validation through external stakeholders covered in Chapters 4 and 6.

It is imperative to note that these simulations are not projections, and the two separate parts (partial equilibrium model and the computable general equilibrium model MAGNET) should not be juxtaposed because they will not necessarily give the same results. The main difference is that the partial equilibrium model relies on data at a very detailed level for a specific commodity, whereas the MAGNET model relies on data at a more aggregate level. Therefore, the complementarity between the two models depends on the policymakers' goals – the MAGNET analysis may prove useful when the interest lies in macroeconomic implications, while the partial equilibrium model allows to zoom in on some specific commodities and supply chains. Both simulations serve as a framework for guiding progress toward a just pathway and realistic FLW reduction targets, and they work on different assumptions (see D1.3 for more details). In Chapter 6, we aim to utilise and apply key insights from both models.

3.1 Partial equilibrium model and MAGNET analysis results

3.1.1 Partial equilibrium model - Mandatory targets (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)

The first part of D1.3 applies the partial equilibrium model described in Deliverable D1.2 to simulate the policy objectives determined in D8.1 on four distinct commodities: chicken, fruit, bread, and milk. It focuses on the mandatory reduction targets, which are a minimum, legally binding FLW reduction goal in each of the policy pathway. However, supply chain actors may voluntarily choose to reduce FLW further against higher abatement costs. The effects of mandatory targets are simulated by imposing a tax on total (i.e., edible and inedible) FLW disposal. Taxes on FLW disposal simulate the increased costs that supply chain actors must bear to achieve the targets set by the policy pathways. Implementing a tax on FLW disposal serves as a broad strategy to reduce FLW, offering economic actors two options: either decrease the quantity of food purchased or lower the FLW rate. Alternative approaches, such as taxing food purchases or subsidising FLW abatement, can also mitigate FLW generation, but these measures directly focus on only one aspect -

either the quantity of purchased food or the FLW rate – whereas a disposal tax provides a more comprehensive mechanism to drive FLW reduction. Thus, the disposal tax was selected to simulate the mandatory targets. Unlike P2, which applies a uniform disposal tax across the entire supply chain to encourage holistic FLW reduction, policy P1 and P3 employ sector-specific FLW disposal taxes to tailor reductions to specific areas of the supply chain. The supply chain model was able to simulate all mandatory targets except for fruit in policy P2. A detailed explanation with the relevant tables showcasing the specific results for each policy pathway and commodity can be found in Chapter 5 of D1.3. In this chapter, we focus on identifying the key overarching results and observations stemming from the simulations.

The first result following from the simulations of the three policy pathways for the four commodities is that the **disposal tax needs to increase significantly to achieve the goals**, with P2 being the costliest to achieve. Even in P3, which has the lowest increase in disposal taxes for milk, taxes increase by 255% for retailer and consumer stages (see pages 26-30 in D1.3 for details). Disposal costs for non-taxed supply chain stages decrease due to reduced overall FLW quantities across the supply chain in each policy pathway. Lower FLW levels reduce demand for disposal services, driving down their prices, which in turn increases edible waste rates at non-taxed stages. This effect is absent in P2, where all stages are subject to disposal taxes, raising their disposal costs.

The second result concerns the **importance of inedible FLW**, whose effect is clearest in P3 and was shown through the comparison of the results for chicken consumption at home (commodity with high inedible FLW rate) and milk consumption at home (commodity without inedible FLW). The simulations show that a commodity without inedible FLW can achieve total FLW reduction targets at lower costs compared to food products containing inedible FLW.

The third observed result are the **cascading effects across the food supply chain**, especially relevant for the processing stage in the fruit and bread supply chain in P1. Processors of these commodities can meet the 10% FL reduction target without an increase in disposal costs through taxes. While their loss rates rise due to lower disposal costs, the reduced demand from downstream supply chain stages is sufficient to lower the absolute quantity of FL. In the case of fruit processors, the reduction even surpasses the policy pathway goal by 4.3 percentage points.

The fourth result reveals a **substitution effect between food consumption at home (FAH) and away from home (FAFH)**. This effect is most pronounced in policy P1 and P3, which target reducing FW at home, increasing the cost of FAH for consumers. Higher costs arise from increased expenses for FW disposal and efforts to reduce waste at home. As a result, consumers partially shift from the more

expensive FAH (with FAH consumption dropping by up to 35% for chicken and fruit in policy P2) to FAFH. However, total food consumption can still decline by up to 30% for fruit in policy P2.

The fifth and last result concerns the **changes in prices** for the four commodities across the supply chain. Food prices generally decrease across the supply chain in policy P1 and P3, except for bread retail prices in P3. In P2, prices show more variation, with increases observed for chicken at the processor, retail, and Hotel Restaurant Institutional (HRI) levels. According to de Gorter et al. (2021), selling prices align with waste rates, but elasticity plays a key role: intermediary prices rise with consumer waste rates under inelastic demand but fall when demand is elastic. However, a crucial complicating factor, especially in P2, was highlighted: disposal taxes can shift demand from inelastic to elastic, causing initial price drops to reverse, potentially exceeding baseline levels.

3.1.2 Partial Equilibrium model - Voluntary targets (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)

This section presents the simulation results for the voluntary FLW reduction targets for 2030 under policy scenarios P1 and P2 across different stages of the supply chain (see Annex IV in D1.3). The voluntary targets were simulated on top of the mandatory targets so that their combination achieves the overall FLW reduction goal. For instance, under P1, there is a mandatory 30% reduction in consumer FW, supplemented by a voluntary 20% reduction, totalling 50%.

Pijpers and Drabik (2025) questioned the economic rationale of voluntary targets, noting that they imply supply chain actors would willingly accept lower profits due to higher abatement costs. To address this, the simulations modelled the targets similarly to MAGNET's approach. The underlying assumption is that voluntary targets encourage investments in new FLW-reducing technologies. These innovations lower abatement costs, enabling the achievement of the voluntary targets while improving profitability. However, the model does not factor in the initial investment costs incurred by supply chain actors. Instead, it focuses on how much abatement costs must decrease to achieve the voluntary targets, offering insights into their feasibility. Targets requiring minimal cost reductions are more likely achievable, as they involve small adjustments to existing technologies. In contrast, achieving substantial abatement costs reductions would require groundbreaking innovations, which are much more difficult to develop.

The simulations found that achieving the voluntary targets for P1 and P3 by 2030 requires significant reductions in abatement costs. For chicken, however, the targets remain unattainable due to the presence of inedible food waste. Notably, the voluntary targets partially offset the substitution effect between FAH and FAFH seen under the mandatory targets. In the mandatory target simulations for P1 and P3, the HRI sector experienced increased food sales compared to the

baseline. However, as FAH abatement costs decrease - making home consumption cheaper - consumers shift back to eating at home, reducing HRI sales (see pages 66-69 in D1.3 for details).

The results show that the supply chain stages without FLW reduction targets generate more FLW than those under the mandatory target scenario. For instance, FW from FAFH consumption more than doubles for bread and milk in both policy pathways compared to the baseline. The impact of FLW reductions on prices is mixed. Under the mandatory targets, prices generally decrease under P1 and P3, except for a rise in the retailer's price of bread under P3. Introducing voluntary targets changes this pattern: in P1, prices remain lower than the baseline but are higher than under the mandatory targets, resulting in a smaller overall price drop. In contrast, P3 experiences sharp price increases under the voluntary targets, fully reversing the earlier reduction and pushing some prices above baseline levels.

3.1.3 MAGNET analysis (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025)

The second part of the simulations consists of a MAGNET model analysis that compares the policy scenarios to our **business-as-usual (BaU) baseline scenario** (see PART II, page 7 in D1.3 for more details).

In the BaU scenario, FLW are projected to decrease by 4,309 million tons (-8.7%) between 2030 and 2050, although some countries show an increase. This reduction is driven by two key changes in consumption patterns. First, a modest shift toward animal-based product consumption, as incomes rise, lowers FLW levels by 2050 in the EU27, as animal-based products typically have lower FLW rates than plant-based products. Second, rising incomes, particularly in southern and eastern European countries, lead to a shift toward food services, reducing FAH consumption. Since waste margins in Distribution and Retail are lower than those for home consumption, this shift further reduces overall FW generation. In this section, we present and cluster the findings for each impact area.

FLW magnitude and composition

The simulations show that as FLW reduction targets are imposed across food commodities, plant-based products (e.g., horticulture and cereals) present the highest absolute reductions, since they have on average the largest FLW volumes and are therefore majorly impacted by the introduction of reduction measures. A parallel trend across commodities is observed for voluntary FLW reductions; however, the imposition of taxes also leads to a moderately stronger decrease of animal-based FLW from meat, dairy, and fish compared to voluntary reductions.

The observed effect is linked to the income effect generated by taxes in P2, which contain the demand for animal food products more than in P3, thereby resulting in lower generation of FLW. Among the scenarios, P1 achieves the greatest

FLW reductions by 2030, especially at the consumer level, cutting households FLW by 80%. While the tax-driven P2 approach also reduces FLW effectively, it does so at a higher economic cost. Consequently, imposing stand-alone taxes on FLW generation (P2) yields a more moderate FLW reduction compared to the combined strategy of taxation and voluntary reduction efforts (P1).

The Economic impacts of FLW reduction pathways on producers

The results show that FLW reductions improve production efficiency either through direct taxation or voluntary measures, leading to lower prices for food commodities - especially in P3. As FLW decreases, producers can maintain the same output with less waste, thereby reducing production costs. This efficiency gain boosts total output, enhancing overall food production and supply in the EU27. The higher supply level results in a moderate decline in average producer prices for food commodities across all scenarios. The price reduction stems from the interplay between improved efficiency and wider availability of food products.

Taxes on FLW generation lead to a smaller decrease in producer food prices compared to voluntary reduction measures. When taxes are imposed at production stages - such as post-harvest handling and storage, manufacturing, and distribution and retail - they introduce extra costs that slightly increase food commodity prices. These additional costs partially offset the price decrease typically associated with efficiency gains from reduced FLW. In contrast, voluntary FLW reduction scenarios avoid the imposition of these extra costs, allowing production efficiency to translate directly into more significant decreases in producer food prices.

Increased food production in the EU27 raises agricultural land use and prices, particularly in southern countries by 2030 and 2050. Scenario P1 leads to the highest land appreciation due to greater production expansion and wage growth, particularly for unskilled workers, due to stronger labour demand compared to tax-driven P2. Wage impacts vary by commodity and country: countries reliant on unskilled labour and horticulture, such as Italy and Spain, see larger gains, while countries focused on meat, dairy, and oil (e.g. Ireland and Lithuania) experience modest increases. In land-scarce, capital-intensive farming countries (e.g. Denmark and the Netherlands), real wage growth remains modest, influenced by rising land prices and a relatively smaller increase in labour demand across scenarios.

The impacts on consumers

Lower food prices boost overall food demand, particularly for plant-based commodities like horticultural products, thereby enhancing food affordability for consumers. Demand rises for horticulture commodities (mainly root and tubers), increasing in 2030 by an average of 1.4% under P2 and slightly higher at 2% under P3, where the absence of taxes removes budget constraints on final consumption.

Food purchasing power improves across all pathways, with P1 achieving the most significant increases. Regional variations are more pronounced in southern Europe - particularly Italy and Portugal - where price reductions are greatest. In Eastern Europe, despite declining wages, an even larger drop in producer prices further enhances food affordability for consumers.

The impact on trade

P1 leads to the largest increase in food imports, especially in Italy and Portugal, as domestic demand drives a decline in exports. Food exports decrease across all scenarios with the most pronounced reductions occurring in P2. In this scenario, higher taxes moderate the drop in food prices, reducing foreign demand for EU27 products compared to P1 and P3, where EU27 food prices fall more sharply. Gross Domestic Product (GDP) effects vary by country. Export-oriented regions experience moderate growth, while countries more dependent on imports may face slight GDP reductions due to increased trade deficits.

The impact on the environment

FLW reductions lower Greenhouse Gas Emissions (GHG) in waste management sectors. These policies notably reduce emissions from waste treatment and collection, particularly under P1, where emissions drop by nearly 7 million tons of CO₂-equivalents by 2030.

However, increased agricultural production and greater use of chemical fertilisers raise emissions in primary agriculture. Similarly, **non-food sectors** experience higher emissions due to rise in non-food demand linked to lower food prices and higher food affordability resulting from FLW reductions. By 2050, the rise in non-food emissions is more contained under P2 (1.7 million tons of CO₂-eq), as taxes constrain consumer budgets and limit non-food demand. In contrast, P3, driven by voluntary reductions, generates an increase of non-food emission of 2.1 million tons of CO₂-eq across the EU27. Overall, reductions in GHG emissions from waste treatment in the EU27 surpass increases from the non-food and agricultural sectors. However, in countries that primarily rely on incineration rather than landfilling for waste disposal, total emissions increase. While landfilling remains the largest source of GHG emissions, incineration and, to a lesser extent, composting also contribute – albeit at significantly lower intensities. Consequently, in countries where FW is predominantly incinerated or composted, emissions reductions in waste treatment are insufficient to offset the growing emissions from agricultural production and non-food sectors. This leads to an overall increase in total emissions. In the Netherlands, Belgium, Luxembourg, and Sweden, higher agriculture-related emissions offset the reductions achieved through waste treatment. Similarly, in Austria and Germany, rising emissions from non-food sectors lead to overall emissions increase under all scenarios by 2030 and 2050. Therefore, FW reduction

in these countries provides **limited emissions benefits**. Additionally, the rise in agricultural production and land use - particularly under P1 - increases fertiliser use, especially for nitrogen-intensive crops, prompting the **urgent need** for more sustainable agricultural practices.

3.2 Reflection on key insights and findings (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)

The simulations of the three FLW-reducing policy options offer valuable insights into defining a 'just' pathway by clarifying its key components and identifying fair and achievable targets in the short and medium term.

The results showed the economic effects of reducing FLW at one stage of the supply chain, along with the cascading effects on other stages. This emphasises how all sectors are connected and interdependent and stresses the need to think carefully about FLW reduction measures and their potential unintended consequences, particularly for more vulnerable actors.

The simulations show that achieving the mandatory targets of the three policy pathways would require substantial taxes on FLW disposal. Although these targets align with the F2F and the SDG 12.3, this finding offers a crucial insight for policymakers: **taxing FLW disposal alone is unlikely to be a realistic option to achieve the FLW reduction goals of the pathways**. Alternative interventions will likely be necessary. The ZeroW project is developing technological innovations within its SILLs that could reduce the costs of edible FLW abatement, helping to decrease FLW quantities. These innovations, outlined in Section 6.3 of this deliverable, could play a pivotal role in creating a just pathway with realistic targets.

Another key finding is the **role of inedible FLW** in reducing overall FLW. Even with technological innovations that lower the abatement costs of edible FLW, the reduction in FLW may remain limited for those commodities with high inedible FLW rates, such as chicken at home. Pijpers and Drabik (2025) suggest that taxing the prices of these commodities could more effectively curb purchases. However, future research is needed to assess the effects of these other interventions. It is also important to note that taxing certain commodities may disproportionately burden vulnerable consumers, potentially undermining the goal of a just transition towards near-zero FLW.

Furthermore, the findings reveal that **sectors not subject to a tax on disposal costs increase their FLW rate when other sectors are taxed**. This is an important consideration for policymakers, who could avoid this outcome by setting FLW targets that prevent increases in FLW for untaxed stages of the supply chain. However, it is important to note that implementing this measure would likely have economic effects that the model could not fully capture.

An important outcome stemming from the simulations is the **decrease in consumption of FAH**, which signifies a trend that should be considered carefully when developing FLW reduction targets. The model does not capture consumer heterogeneity. Thus, it is not possible to determine which types of consumers will be most affected. However, a reduction of up to 35% in consumption of FAH is significant even if partially offset by eating more FAFH. For instance, there is a predicted 30% decrease in total fruit consumption in P2 due to the expected 50% reduction target at the consumer level. This raises concerns about food accessibility, as reducing the availability of a healthy commodity like fruit could disproportionately affect lower-income households. Such concern highlights the **potential unintended consequences of higher targets**. Pijpers and Drabik (2025) emphasise the importance of elasticities as a driver of the outcomes, as the cascading effects upstream in the supply chain differ when the demand for a commodity becomes elastic or inelastic. Policymakers need to consider this when weighting environmental benefits (which are not included in these simulations) against FLW reduction costs. The results of the voluntary targets further emphasise these concerns, especially the **need to lower abatement costs significantly**.

The MAGNET analysis reinforces these insights by offering a **complementary macroeconomic perspective** and highlighting the related implications. Both direct taxation on FLW generation at various stages of the FSC and voluntary reductions are effective measures of reducing FLW in the EU27. To achieve a 50% FLW reduction by 2030 through taxation (P2), a uniform 25% tax on FLW generation and collection costs would need to be applied across all stages of the FSC, affecting both producers and consumers. More ambitious targets, such as a 90% FLW reduction by 2050, would require significantly higher taxes—potentially up to 110%—to prompt the necessary behavioural and operational changes. While taxation imposes costs on both producers and consumers, its broader economic impact remains relatively moderate, especially when compared to scenarios where FLW reductions are achieved primarily through voluntary measures (P1 and P3). Although voluntary reductions may be preferable for avoiding direct costs to supply chain agents, the most effective approach depends on the overall economic impact of these measures. In the EU27, the Distribution and Retail and Consumption stages are the primary hotspots for FLW generation and should therefore be prioritised for policy interventions to achieve significant FLW reductions by 2030 and 2050. Among food categories, plant-based commodities - particularly cereals, grains, and horticultural products - constitute the largest share of FLW in the EU27. Therefore, prioritising policies targeting these commodities and the primary hotspots would result in the most substantial overall reductions in FLW compared to other categories and actors.

Nevertheless, regardless of the chosen measure to reduce FLW, the simulations reveal several **unintended spillover effects** that policymakers need to consider when designing a just pathway. These effects could undermine the expected benefits of FLW interventions. For example, improved production efficiency, due to reduced food losses during production, leads to an increase in agrifood production, particularly for commodities that are already FLW-intensive and benefit the most from reductions (e.g., cereals, grains, horticultural products). While the growth in agrifood supplies across the EU27 benefits consumers by lowering producer prices, it also intensifies the demand for key production inputs, most notably land use. This **increase in agricultural land use** has been identified as a major driver of environmental impacts with negative effects on several ecosystems, such as biodiversity loss (Maxwell et al., 2016; Power, 2010; Leclere et al., 2020). Policymakers would need to carefully manage this spillover effect. The MAGNET simulations indicate that imposing taxes can help reduce the scale and magnitude of economic spillovers, as the additional costs generated by taxes lead to more moderate reductions in production prices, compared to voluntary measures with no additional costs. Consequently, taxes would help control the increase in production, leading to a more moderate rise in land use. Nonetheless, the simulations showcase how the increased production drives higher labour demand, which leads to a moderate increase in agricultural wages across the EU27. Unskilled workers benefit more significantly than skilled workers, helping to narrow the wage gap by 2050. This effect is more pronounced in countries with labour-intensive agricultural sectors, where increased production boosts labour demand, while it is more moderate in countries with capital-intensive agricultural sectors. In line with the previous economic spillover, this rise in average wages is also more limited in scenarios with stand-alone FLW taxes compared to those driven by voluntary reductions.

Finally, crucial **environmental spillovers** are identified in the increased emissions from non-food sectors and agricultural sectors, driven by higher demand for non-food goods and the increased use of chemical fertilisers in agriculture. While reducing FLW in the EU27 significantly reduces emissions from waste treatment and collection, these benefits are offset by increasing emissions in primary agriculture and non-food sectors, particularly in higher-income countries with input-intensive agricultural practices. The cause of this lies in the increase in production and greater use of chemical fertilisers to sustain it, highlighting the **urgent need** to invest and shift towards **more sustainable agricultural practices**. This shift is imperative to bend the curve of rising emissions when the EU27 see increases in food production. Additionally, the simulations point out how higher demand for non-food commodities linked to lower consumer spending on food products would exacerbate emissions from non-food sectors, which present higher emissions than

food sectors. This potential rebound effect in other emission-intensive activities is a **vital warning** to consider when designing FLW reduction policies that target food systems. If non-food related impacts are not considered, policy measures are likely to generate unintended negative effects.

The simulations offer a preliminary framework to tackle these spillover effects, as taxes on FLW generation prove to be more effective in containing spillovers than stand-alone voluntary reductions. Following the MAGNET analysis' macroeconomic perspective, the moderate negative effects observed in the presence of a large tax (around 110%) that allows to reduce FLW by 90% indicate that direct taxation may be more suitable to contain spillovers even if it may result in additional economic burdens for the EU27 FSC actors. In this regard, Bartelings and Gatto (2025) offer some final recommendations, reflecting on how price-based mechanisms usually tend to prove more effective at promoting sustainable behaviours and reducing FLW than 'soft' measures such as awareness campaigns or educational programs (Latka et al., 2021; Katare et al., 2017; Hamilton et al., 2019). In the simulations, consumers spend a limited share of their budget on food products, facing a low elasticity of demand (demand not changing significantly when food prices change). Nonetheless, since incomes would likely be impacted through changes in wages, devising FLW reduction policies requires considering national differences among the EU27.

Based on the simulation results, Bartelings and Gatto (2025) recommend prioritising tax policies in higher-income northern European countries featuring capital-intensive agricultural sectors, such as Denmark and the Netherlands. A tax-based approach would target FLW at the Distribution and Retail and Consumption stages, effectively mitigating negative spillover effects by limiting excessive increases in agricultural production, which are associated with higher fertiliser use and GHG emissions. Moreover, consumers in wealthier countries are more adaptable to price changes, meaning that tax imposition could help reduce spillover effects into non-food demand sectors, curbing GHG emissions. Conversely, in southern European countries with labour-intensive agricultural sectors such as Italy and Spain, policies should prioritise voluntary FLW reduction. These voluntary measures would foster positive socio-economic impacts, stimulating production and job creation. To complement these efforts, modest tax-based incentives could be introduced, striking a balance that promotes producer efficiency without imposing significant additional costs. Where animal-based production dominates, the authors suggest a blended approach combining voluntary measures with moderate tax interventions. The priority would be to target plant-based commodities in these regions (which account for a large share of FLW), enhancing food security and benefiting unskilled wages. However, the gap between skilled and unskilled workers should be further addressed through investments in skill

development for agricultural innovation, encouraging workers to adopt sustainable practices.

In the following chapters, we integrate these key insights from the simulation results with a conceptual framework for a 'just pathway' (Chapter 4), using a unique design described in Chapter 5. By validating these results with input from stakeholders across the FSC, we outline intermediate FLW reduction targets in Chapter 6 that represent a step toward a just pathway for 2050.

4. Defining a 'just pathway'

Figure 6: Overview of the conceptual framework

Leading institutions, such as the United Nations (UN), have explored the challenges and opportunities of transforming food systems, with the 'just transition pathway' emerging as a key approach to ensuring all FSC stakeholders are involved. The first step is to define what 'just' means and how to achieve it. This literature review examines the state of play of a 'just' transition and develops a conceptual framework. The first section assesses the current food system, focusing on key actors, vulnerabilities, and key justice dimensions. The second examines potential transformative changes needed for reform, including food perceptions and market practices, shorter supply chains, and inclusive innovation. The final section highlights stakeholder engagement and collaborative approaches as essential to achieving this transition, along with relevant frameworks that support its implementation.

4.1 Assessing the status quo: actors, vulnerabilities and justice dimensions in the food system

The food system is a complex, multilevel network shaped by socio-economic, political, and ecological factors, often masking systemic vulnerabilities that disproportionately affect certain groups (Moragues et al., 2017). Understanding dimensions of justice is key to identifying root causes of these vulnerabilities and enabling transformative change. In broad terms, *a just pathway implies a transition to a more sustainable, fair and inclusive food system - reducing environmental impact in the short term, fostering economic growth in the medium term, and strengthening resilience against climate change in the long term.*

4.1.1 Mapping the Food Supply Chain (FSC)

For developing a just pathway, it is imperative to ensure a **balanced allocation of positive and negative impacts for all food actors involved**. A pragmatic and fair way to achieve a balanced allocation would be to select ambassadors from each chain of the food sector and have them engage in a participative dialogue with policymakers to co-create a strategy and set realistic medium and long-term targets. These ambassadors would function as representatives of their sector and could be individuals from each stage of the FSC (see figure 7 below).

Figure 7: Overview of the Food Supply Chain (FSC)

Each group within the food system faces distinct vulnerabilities shaped by their position in the supply chain, access to resources, decision-making power, and market opportunities. **Asymmetrical power relations** are a key driver of these vulnerabilities, thereby marginalising some stakeholders (Moragues et al., 2017). External actors of the FSC also influence these power imbalances. Weak institutional capacities and fragmented governance compound the issue, restricting the ability of smaller actors to influence policies or access necessary support systems (Moragues et al., 2017). Recognising these diverse vulnerabilities is critical for addressing systemic inequities and fostering resilience across the food system.

4.1.2 Identifying the vulnerable groups in the status quo

Before assessing potential reforms for a just transition, it is crucial to identify vulnerable groups and the factors driving their vulnerability in the status quo. These groups face intersecting socio-economic, political, and environmental pressures (Moragues et al., 2017). A just pathway to near-zero FLW by 2050 must account for

their disadvantageous position. Through bilateral and plenary discussions, the ZeroW Policy team identified the following groups:

- **In all stages of the FSC:**

- Most at-risk workers in those roles expected to be phased out by the transition.
- Migrant workers who may continue to lack legal protection, labour rights, food literacy, access to knowledge and language barriers.
- Minority communities marginalised from the mainstream economic system due to legal restrictions, language barriers or discrimination, such as immigrant populations, ethnic groups (e.g., Roma groups in Europe), religious and LGBTQ+ communities.
- Informal food vendors who may retain no formal recognition during the transition.
- Alternative food networks, which focus more on social goals rather than profit, thus struggling to compete with large-scale distributors.
- Women, youth, elders:
 - Women are subject to gender inequality which leads to "discriminatory social norms and rules affecting women and girls". Moreover, "formal policies and strategies may increasingly identify the constraints and inequalities that women face, but few national policies specify objectives to address them" (FAO, 2023)
 - The youth are particularly vulnerable to economic instability, limited access to resources, educational gaps, and social and political marginalisation due to less influence in decision-making processes (Slycan Trust, 2021; Ahmed, 2020).
 - Elders are also subject to food insecurity as many live on fixed incomes, such as pension or social security. The digital divide and generational replacement increase their vulnerability during the transition (Leung and Wolfson, 2020).

- **Producers**

- Agricultural workers, especially:
 - Farmers in lower-income countries and regions, more vulnerable to job insecurity.
 - Female farmers, who can be less connected to ecosystems that provide support when implementing innovations (FAO, 2023).
 - Older farmers with no succession prospects for their farm, who consequently find it unproductive to invest money and resources in innovation.

- Small-scale farmers, who are especially vulnerable to the technological changes that come with innovation and to the current balance of power that favours markets over farmers.
- Small-scale fishermen who lack access to adequate infrastructure, and large-scale fishermen who encounter significant FW due to infrastructure limitations and the discarding of low-value fish according to a stakeholder in the fishing sector (Racioppo et al., 2021).
- **Food Processors and Packaging Companies**, more specifically the ones impacted by:
 - technological acceptance and market demand and regulation: as new processing and packaging technologies require significant investment, some processors are vulnerable to market dynamics that may not favour innovation, especially if consumers are not receptive (D'haese et al., 2023).
- **Distributors**, more specifically the ones that:
 - lack cold storage infrastructure and transportation networks - a key vulnerability for some logistics and transportation companies. Perishable foods are highly susceptible to spoilage during transport, especially when cold chains are inadequate, which leads to significant FW (Racioppo et al., 2021).
- **Retailers**, more specifically the ones impacted by:
 - market dynamics and consumer behaviour: some supermarkets and grocery stores, driven by consumer demands for 'perfect' produce, often discard food that is still consumable. Additionally, they face challenges from food neophobia and technophobia, which hinder the acceptance of innovations to reduce waste (D'haese et al., 2023).
- **End consumers**, especially the ones impacted by:
 - economic constraints, knowledge gaps, and systemic barriers: many are price-sensitive, which limits their ability to adopt sustainable food choices, especially when environmentally friendly options are more expensive. Cultural norms and limited awareness increase FW at the household level. These vulnerabilities are compounded by the ineffectiveness of stand-alone awareness campaigns, as systemic factors and consumer fatigue hinder meaningful behavioural change (D'haese et al., 2023).

In addition to the information mentioned above, there are crucial **overarching challenges** that make the transition possibly unjust and could negatively affect these vulnerable groups, such as the **economic and bureaucratic costs** that could be expected from the transition for all stakeholders of the FSC. For instance, significant investments are needed to improve storage, transportation, and

processing facilities to reduce FLW. Day-to-day operational costs may also increase as businesses adopt new practices and technologies to reduce FLW, including the maintenance of new equipment and systems. Bureaucratic costs can even be more pressing. For instance, regulatory compliance can often be very costly to businesses as they may need to invest in compliance measures such as reporting and auditing (McKinsey Global Institute, 2022). Besides the economic disparities that may further widen the gap between wealthy and poorer regions, inaccessible technology, data gaps throughout the supply chain, market dynamics asking for cosmetically perfect produce, and inconsistent policies may contribute to making this transition unjust.

Another factor that exacerbates the conditions of vulnerable groups is **climate change**: vulnerable groups are particularly susceptible to environmental issues such as drought, floods or pests, and loss of biodiversity, which worsen existing inequalities and perpetuate the socio-economic disparities (Moragues et al., 2017). The **demographic change** also has an impact on these groups, who face challenges related to the depletion of rural areas.

Nonetheless, while these costs and challenges can be substantial, the long-term benefits of reducing FLW - including improved food security, enhanced environmental sustainability, and economic savings - can outweigh the initial investments. One of the objectives of the just transition is to ensure that these costs are managed in a way that does not disproportionately burden vulnerable populations. The next section delves into the dimensions of justice that should be considered to make the transition holistic.

4.1.3 Dimensions of justice

The transition aims to create an inclusive, participatory environment where all voices contribute to the reduction strategy. A just pathway focuses on vulnerable groups, ensuring support to the actors who face **pre-existing inequalities** and those who might face **arising challenges**. To achieve near-zero FLW by 2050, this means a fair approach to reducing food waste across the supply chain, ensuring that benefits and responsibilities are shared justly among all stakeholders.

The lack of a truly transformative and socially just food policy is a recognised shortcoming of the *F2F strategy*, which failed to address the social dimensions of food and propose effective and ambitious measures to tackle the inequalities and unsustainable practices permeating the current food system (Jackson et al., 2021). Thus, by reflecting on the status quo, the ZeroW Policy Team defined a just pathway towards 'near-zero FLW by 2050' based on **three key criteria**, or **core dimensions of 'justice'** in the food system (European Environment Agency, 2023):

- *Distributional* – Identifying who bears the costs and who enjoys the benefits of the transition. The solutions must not burden those that can least afford

it, and policies should not worsen the conditions of these vulnerable actors, especially small or medium-size holders. Likewise occurs with the benefits, which should be equally distributed.

- *Procedural* – It is crucial to change the narrative of blame towards some members of the FSC, including consumers. All stakeholders must be included in the discussions and decision-making process.
- *Recognition* – While the transition should be inclusive and leave no one behind, it remains to be seen whether inequalities can be feasibly addressed. If this cannot be achieved, it must be acknowledged, and steps should be taken to amend it or justly compensate those who cannot receive the benefits.

The transition must be approached **holistically**, with particular attention to its **social dimension**. It is crucial to communicate that new innovations should not jeopardise job security for producers, while emphasising the long-term benefits of moving away from unsustainable practices within the food system. Addressing workers' perceptions is vital to prevent misinterpretations of the transition, which could undermine its success. In line with the **recognition dimension** of justice, it is essential to acknowledge and address inequalities faced by vulnerable groups, ensuring that they are integrated throughout the process. Clear communication of the transition's value is essential for engaging all stakeholders, alongside raising awareness of the just transition concept. By prioritising practical solutions and fostering behavioural change, while maintaining ambitious targets, the transition can progress more effectively and sustain stakeholder support.

The challenges to achieving a just transition are not only social but also structural, stemming from the **fragmented nature** of the food sector. Bureaucratic and administrative barriers, alongside a lack of coordination between diverse actors in the value chain, hinder the integration of policies that support equitable participation (EIT Food, 2020; Marsden et al., 2018). These issues disproportionately affect smaller actors who have limited access to funding, further exacerbating inequalities (Mennig, 2024; Said et al., 2018). To address these **distributional and procedural challenges**, stronger sectoral connections are needed to improve integration and ensure fair access to resources. Bridging the gap between researchers, farmers, and policymakers can help translate knowledge into practice and ensure that the benefits of the transition are widely shared, particularly among those who are most vulnerable (Mennig, 2024; Said et al., 2018).

To ensure a just transition, it is essential to complement these dimensions of justice with efforts to overcome systemic barriers such as the digital divide, which amplifies existing inequalities and limits equitable participation across the FSC.

4.1.4 The digital divide

The digital divide, a key challenge in the FSC, refers to the gap between those with access to information and communication technologies and those without. In developing regions, and even in rural areas of developed countries, actors often lack access to digital tools, exacerbating inequalities. Farmers and fishermen, for instance, may lack the resources and training needed to adopt digital technologies that could improve their productivity and market access (FAO, 2019). As industries and decision-makers praise digital technologies like sensors, robotics, and AI as a “solution to growing social and environmental crises” (Rotz et al., 2019, p.112), disparities in access further **deepen existing inequalities** (Smith et al., 2023). Addressing this divide is crucial to ensure vulnerable actors can benefit from technological advancements, as poor connectivity, low digital literacy, and high costs disproportionately affect smallholder farmers and rural communities (Marie, 2024).

Digital tools can create a **‘trolley dilemma’**, balancing the benefits of increased food production with negative societal impacts on marginalised groups and environmental sustainability (Lioutas et al., 2021). AI and big data are expected to improve decision-making, resource efficiency, and reduce environmental impact through precision farming, with projections of a 70% improvement in farm efficiency globally by 2050 (Lioutas et al., 2021). However, risks include a concentration of power in large agribusinesses, the exclusion of smallholder farmers, and the displacement of low-wage migrant labour due to automation, which bypasses the social and political complexities of managing this workforce (Lioutas et al., 2021; Rotz et al., 2019). Furthermore, increased productivity can lead to ecological impacts like reduced biodiversity and soil degradation (Lioutas et al., 2021). In merchandise flow and sales, digital disparities limit access to distribution infrastructure, visibility to buyers, and the ability to track market trends, regulate supply volumes, and adjust pricing (Smith and Taylor, 2023).

The following section summarises the potential policy interventions identified by the ZeroW Policy Team to address the challenges faced within the current food systems and the regulatory initiatives that could accompany a just transition.

4.2 Transformative changes for a just transition

4.2.1 Reforming the food system and market practices

A **shift from viewing food as a ‘commodity’ to a ‘good’** could be key in reforming the food system (Vivero-Pol, 2017). Currently, food is treated primarily as a tradable commodity, focusing on traits like durability, external beauty, and standardisation, while also neglecting its nutritional value (Vivero-Pol, 2017). This approach has been exacerbated by inflation, particularly during crises like COVID-19 (Ihle et al., 2020).

Shifting to view food as a 'good' would move away from market-driven fluctuations and help establish fairer pricing mechanisms that better reflect its true value. This would not only benefit consumers but also ensure fair compensation for producers. Moreover, studies show that food prices influence diet quality, especially for low-income groups, where the high cost of healthy food exacerbates health and socioeconomic disparities (Darmon and Drewnowski, 2015). This perception shift could have drawbacks depending on its implementation. To assess food costs impartially, an independent government-paid inspector could be appointed.

An **independent inspector** could also help reform 'take-back practices' at the supplier-retailer interface (Eriksson et al., 2017). These practices involve retailers returning unsold or defective products to suppliers, which can be used unfairly to reject products due to lower demand. An unbiased inspector would ensure fair compensation to producers, but inspections must be systematic, not ad-hoc, to avoid dissuading producers from requesting inspections.

Furthermore, **unfair marketing practices** in the FSC continue to disadvantage certain actors, leading to both economic losses and increased FLW. The EU Directive 2019/633 addresses 16 such practices— ten categorised as 'black' and six as 'grey' (FAO, 2024). A key issue is that many producers operate in a system where a limited number of buyers, including some processors, distributors, and retailers, hold significant influence. This imbalance is further exacerbated by producers' limited legal and financial resources to challenge unfair practices. While the Directive establishes a baseline level of protection and harmonisation rules for farmers and operators in the FSC, achieving a just transition toward near-zero FLW requires **stronger enforcement, improved monitoring, and more effective implementation by MS.**

4.2.2 (Gradually) shortening the Food Supply Chain (FSC)

The food system would benefit from **more direct relationships** between producers and small sellers, **reducing FLW and addressing power imbalances in the FSC.** Currently, the market's status quo favours large players, limiting producers' ability to set prices. Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), which reduce intermediaries, would give producers more control over pricing and reduce dependency on large markets (Drejerska and Sobczak, 2023). Strengthening SFSCs would enhance producers' economic sustainability and offer opportunities to reduce FLW. Boosting the commercialisation of proximity products, which are locally produced and consumed, can help meet growing consumer demand for sustainable, fresh, and quality goods. These 'kilometre zero' products minimise environmental impacts and provide market opportunities for businesses (Torreblanca, 2020). While scaling up commercialisation presents challenges - such as limited production, logistical difficulties, and competition from mass-produced goods - technological

advancements and digital platforms linking local producers with consumers can help address these issues (Bayir et al., 2022).

A more direct relationship between producers and sellers would offer additional **environmental benefits**, such as the development of local markets. This would reduce transportation needs, significantly reduce FLW, and improve food donation opportunities. Strengthening food value chain connectivity enhances a food system's capacity to respond to shocks and stresses, building climate resilience and ensuring a more secure food supply (Elechi et al., 2022). However, this reform should not involve a 'communal' initiative; local markets should gradually replace mainstream markets, particularly in metropolitan areas. A phased approach is essential to ensure feasibility and acceptance (Elechi et al., 2022).

The process would begin with **creating logistical spaces** to facilitate direct producer-seller relationships, using public infrastructure (e.g. Mercasa in Spain) to support access to facilities, digitalisation, sustainable last-mile transport, and communication. Stakeholders, such as food logistics hubs like CAAB S.p.A. in Bologna, should be involved. Additionally, promoting alternative public food distribution networks, such as farmers' markets and Community Supported Agriculture (CSA), is crucial. These networks, with a social approach, offer fair prices for producers and consumers, supporting social and agroecological criteria. CSA strengthens agricultural production, boosts incomes, and builds climate resilience (Elechi et al., 2022).

An **evaluation of the economic costs** of establishing SFSCs is necessary, as the imbalance of power may restrict participation to those who can afford it. Solutions will vary by context, including increasing local food quotas through targets and incentives, expanding networks for local producers, and ensuring their products reach more than just small markets. Key stakeholders, including local political institutions, must be engaged, while fostering technological innovation (e.g., repurposing expired products) and developing business models like food banks (Biesbroek et al., 2018). However, red-tape barriers could exclude vulnerable groups, such as small-scale farmers and minority communities. Political changes could also hinder the initiative, particularly at the local level, where funding priorities often shift. Additionally, some producers may be unaware of new local distribution networks, so targeted dissemination and advertising are essential.

4.2.3 Bridging the digital divide: inclusive innovation

Building on the challenges of the digital divide previously outlined, this section explores practical solutions to foster inclusivity and equitable access to digital innovations across the food system.

Bridging the digital divide in the food system requires **coordinated efforts** to improve infrastructure, provide affordable technologies, and offer targeted training, particularly for marginalised groups (Smith and Taylor, 2023). Inclusive digitalisation promotes food security, economic resilience, and sustainability (FAO, 2019). Policies should consider factors such as education, attitudes toward sustainability, and risk tolerance, which influence digital adoption (Rizzo et al., 2023).

Vulnerable groups, especially small-scale producers, often lack digital literacy, making online resources insufficient. Proactive outreach through **tailored information and familiar communication** channels is essential to ensure that producers' concerns are addressed. To encourage adoption, economic benefits and structured support are needed (Rizzo et al., 2023). Digital inclusion can be promoted by connecting vulnerable producers to education, training, and relevant networks, such as through workshops and expert consultations. Local digital innovation hubs should be strengthened to support at-risk groups. An example is the European SmartAgriHubs project, which links vulnerable farmers to innovation ecosystems. Digital exclusion also affects sectors like fishing, where fishermen similarly lack awareness of beneficial digital tools. Increasing visibility and demonstrating the value of these solutions can foster adoption.

For a just transition, especially for farmers without successors, incentives like **financial support, cooperative models, and long-term partnerships** are essential to encourage participation in digital innovations (Rizzo et al., 2023). However, as digitalisation grows, concerns over data ownership arise, with private companies increasingly controlling agricultural data. This raises issues of autonomy and transparency, as many technologies prioritise profit over improving labour conditions (Rotz et al., 2019). Ensuring producers have access to and control over their data is crucial.

Incentivising **data sharing** across the supply chain requires educational campaigns and transparent practices to improve product tracking and food safety (Kosior and Młodawska, 2024). A code of conduct for data acquisition and processing is needed to ensure ethical practices. While the EU's Code of Conduct on Agricultural Data Sharing is a step forward, further improvements are required to enhance clarity, accessibility, and regulatory certainty in data governance (European Union, 2020).

4.2.4 Incentivising and advancing FLW reduction: monitoring and measurement

To effectively incentivise and advance FLW reduction during the transition, two key elements must be prioritised: monitoring and measurement (Cattaneo et al., 2021). Robust monitoring systems are essential for tracking progress, and **investing in data infrastructure and technology** is crucial for enabling transparent data sharing and fostering collaboration among stakeholders (OECD, 2025).

For instance, exploring financial incentives for businesses that successfully reduce waste - such as lower garbage or recycling fees - could be beneficial. However, any incentive system must be established transparently and efficiently, accompanied by a robust monitoring framework. **Regulations** should require stakeholders to disclose waste amounts, providing a baseline for setting targets. Achieving this will demand **investment in infrastructure, planning, and new technologies**, incurring financial costs that must be considered. Additionally, this approach must balance potential drawbacks, as entities with greater financial and technological resources may benefit disproportionately. For example, processors implementing advanced automation to measure FLW may face high costs, while small-scale producers and informal vendors may struggle to even access or benefit from such policies.

Moreover, excessive paperwork and bureaucratic requirements could exclude vulnerable groups, including small-scale producers, minority communities, and individuals with limited digital literacy (such as the elderly), who may face challenges accessing key information or support (Biesbroek et al., 2018). If not implemented correctly, the initiative could also increase the risk of fraud, with stakeholders potentially falsifying waste reduction data to obtain financial incentives. Without a **standardised quantification method** - currently lacking - data collection and reliability would be significantly undermined (Cattaneo et al., 2021).

Building on the necessary reforms discussed in this section, the following one delves into stakeholder engagement and the equitable distribution of responsibilities, emphasising the importance of collaborative approaches to addressing vulnerabilities within the food system and ensuring a just transition toward reducing FLW.

4.3 Stakeholder engagement and equitable distribution of responsibilities

Various actors play important roles in addressing the issue of FLW. The engagement of **local actors**, who are often closest to the food system's vulnerabilities, is particularly critical. Achieving near-zero FLW by 2050 through a just pathway requires a fair and balanced approach to significantly reducing FLW throughout the entire supply chain, from production to consumption. By representing diverse interests, these stakeholders contribute to creating multifaceted solutions that reflect the complexities of the food system and prioritise systemic change.

4.3.1 The role of external actors in the transition

External actors in the traditional FSC, such as cities, food banks, and NGOs, play key roles in addressing systemic vulnerabilities. The way FW is framed influences policy decisions and determines stakeholder responsibility (Mesiranta et al., 2022). Micro-

level solutions, such as food donations or behavioural nudging, and macro-level solutions, like circular economy models, are essential for creating comprehensive solutions that promote systemic change (Mesiranta et al., 2022).

Food banks face challenges and ethical dilemmas in addressing food system vulnerabilities. For instance, a decrease in FLW can paradoxically reduce the food available for distribution. Additionally, food banks often receive unhealthy unsold foods, creating a dilemma about whether to redistribute these or focus on healthier options. Regulatory clarity is needed on distributing food past its 'use by' date. The distinction between private food-sharing initiatives and food banks, particularly regarding communal kitchens, raises liability concerns (Rivera et al., 2023). Ensuring that food banks are properly considered in policy frameworks is essential for creating a fair and effective food system.

NGOs are critical in advocating for marginalised groups and blocking developments that may exacerbate inequalities, such as certain biotechnological interventions (Moragues et al., 2017). Local governments and cities are crucial in integrating food sovereignty and the right to food into policy frameworks, often through green procurement and supporting small producers (Moragues et al., 2017; European Commission, 2008). These actors are uniquely positioned to challenge power imbalances, promote democratic decision-making, and ensure that food security policies align with broader social and environmental goals. Local and regional governments, often responsible for implementing concrete actions, are more effective in these areas, although many lack the political will or capacity to make significant progress.

Best practices often emerge from local governments, with **school systems** being key drivers of change. For example, free school meals can play a crucial role in addressing food insecurity and educating children about reducing food waste. However, the lack of a minimum food procurement criterion in the EU hampers progress. A more systematic approach, such as making food procurement criteria mandatory in public tenders, could stimulate a broader shift. While some cities, like Copenhagen, have advanced in local supply chains, others lag behind. The EU should set minimum procurement criteria to drive the transition, using examples from frontrunner cities to guide policy development. Flexibility is necessary to ensure the market can adapt, and local engagement is critical in implementing these changes effectively. The experience of cities like Copenhagen, which has been developing local supply chains for over 15 years, demonstrates the feasibility of meeting 2030 targets with the right support and regulatory frameworks (Lassen et al., 2023).

4.3.2 Collaborative approaches to address food system vulnerabilities

Fostering dialogue among stakeholders ensures that FLW reduction strategies are effective, inclusive, and equitable, addressing the needs of all involved (Moragues et

al., 2017). Tackling food system vulnerabilities requires governance that prioritises collaboration and inclusivity at multiple scales, addressing structural issues like unequal power dynamics, poor coordination, and limited institutional capacity (Moragues et al., 2017). **Engaging local actors in decision-making** ensures that community-specific needs and systemic inequalities are considered, leading to more tailored and inclusive solutions (Aggarwal et al., 2023). **Collaborative framing** at the local level helps distribute responsibilities more equitably, enabling diverse actors to play a role in addressing food waste (Mesiranta et al., 2022).

Inclusive policy dialogue can be fostered through initiatives like **Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)**, which build trust and encourage participation from governments, businesses, and NGOs (OECD, 2025). Strengthening PPPs and ensuring regular stakeholder dialogue is essential for sharing best practices and innovations. Local levels play a critical role in creating opportunities for meaningful collaboration and ensuring effective implementation.

Co-creation is key for transforming food systems, promoting collaboration between stakeholders like farmers, processors, retailers, consumers, and researchers (EIT Food, 2020). By involving all parties in ideation and implementation, co-creation ensures diverse perspectives are reflected, promotes transparency, and fosters shared responsibility. This approach can lead to sustainable practices, reduce FW, and encourage eco-friendly business models, making the transition to a resilient and just food system more inclusive.

Viewing FLW through a **systemic lens** highlights the need to embed circular economy principles into governance frameworks. This includes collaboration between producers, processors, and retailers to redesign supply chains, reducing waste and valorising surplus resources (Borrello et al., 2016). Circular economy initiatives also engage consumers in waste reduction practices, such as upcycling and redistributing surplus food. By co-creating resource-efficient systems, these strategies not only address FLW but also enhance resilience and sustainability across the food value chain.

4.3.3 Applying frameworks for a just transition

Strategies should ensure equitable outcomes, particularly for vulnerable groups. Interventions must be designed and evaluated using **frameworks that prioritise justice**, such as the **APEASE framework** (Acceptability, Practicability, Effectiveness, Affordability, Spill-over effects, and Equity; FutureLearn, 2025). These criteria ensure that interventions reduce FLW while being fair and inclusive. Acceptability ensures alignment with the values of affected communities, while practicability ensures that interventions are feasible within existing infrastructures. Effectiveness measures whether interventions achieve desired outcomes and value for money, ensuring benefits reach the most disadvantaged. Affordability ensures access for all,

especially those facing financial constraints. Spill-over effects assess unintended consequences, and equity prioritises actions that benefit those most affected by food insecurity or poverty (FutureLearn, 2025).

While APEASE is comprehensive, it lacks focus on the role of social networks in intervention success. The **EAST framework** (Easy, Attractive, Social, and Timely) incorporates this, emphasising the importance of timing in interventions (Hallsworth et al., 2024). Additionally, the **Triple Bottom Line** (TBL) framework balances economic, social, and environmental sustainability (Elkington, 1997). TBL ensures that sustainability efforts create long-term value across all pillars: economic stability, social inclusion, and reduced environmental impact. When integrated, TBL offers a holistic approach to a sustainable, just food system, aligning with the well-being of all stakeholders, particularly the most vulnerable. Using frameworks like APEASE, EAST, and TBL can ensure fairness throughout the transition, ensuring no one is left behind.

5. Methodology

The goal of this deliverable is to understand and indicate a ‘just’ transition pathway to near-zero FLW in 2050 (Chapter 4) and to furthermore set intermediate EU FLW reduction targets. In the following months, this objective will be finalised by delivering short- to medium-term FLW policy recommendations supporting this ambition and directly stemming from the progress achieved so far (Task 8.3).

In the previous tasks within WP8, the ZeroW Policy Team developed a trend pathway looking into the future based on historical trends and with no significant changes to current policies, innovation, and consumer behaviour. With the completion of D8.1, the team formulated alternative, distinctively different, pathways aimed at achieving a near-zero FLW food system (see figure 8 below). These pathways have been validated through the organisation of 3 WGs that explored three key areas: Policy, Innovation, Consumer Behaviour. Additional bilateral interviews with external stakeholders further strengthened the formulation of the three pathways. As shown in the previous chapters, the pathways have been subsequently assessed using both a quantitative approach (ZeroW WP1, FLW modelling) and a qualitative approach (through the roundtable WGs). The research design is explained in detail in the next sections.

Figure 8: Different pathways towards near-zero FLW (D'haese et al., 2023)

5.1 Research design and data collection

The quantitative approach was provided by the ZeroW WP1 team (led by the Wageningen University and Research - WUR) who developed and used economic models to understand and analyse the effects of various policies (taxing FLW disposal and voluntary reduction measures) to reduce FLW in the supply chain. The partial equilibrium model developed by WP1 and the CGE (MAGNET) model developed by WUR cover all stages of the FSC and include the ways of disposing of

FW, such as landfill/incineration, land/sewage, and donation, which have proved useful in quantifying to what extent restrictions imposed on FLW disposal can contribute to its reduction. The macro-level results of the MAGNET analysis provided important insights into the effects of FLW reduction on the GDP of the EU and employment in agriculture and food processing sectors. Deliverable D1.2 explains the full supply chain model with all underlying assumptions and Deliverable 1.3 reiterates the most important aspects (see Chapter 3 in D1.3). The data used for both parts of the simulations come from publicly available databases.⁴

5.2 Combining a quantitative and qualitative approach to set the targets

In this section, we define how we combined a) the policy pathways described in D8.1; b) the key findings and inputs from the modelling simulations detailed in D1.3; c) the conceptual framework on the 'just pathway'; d) the validation and insights from the FSC stakeholders who participated in the roundtables or provided feedback via other means (e.g., written questionnaire).

To set just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets towards 2050 that would meet the requirement of the *F2FAction Plan* (Proposal for EU-level targets for FW reduction), the ZeroW Policy Team devised the following approach, combining qualitative and quantitative inputs defined in the previous sections. The qualitative approach was provided by the ZeroW Policy Team (led by Safe Food Advocacy Europe) who developed a conceptual framework on the 'just' pathway towards near-zero FLW in 2050 and further validated the findings of the FLW modelling through roundtable WGs. Firstly, the team focused on the development of the conceptual framework (see Chapter 4), revisiting the outcomes of the three WGs organised between May and July 2023. These WGs explored the interactions, potential of synergies and/or trade-offs among the three key areas - Policy, Innovation, Consumer Behaviour - towards achieving a near-zero FLW system.

In parallel, the team held regular ad-hoc meetings with WP1, discussing the progress of the FLW modelling simulations and informing different facets when required. Ahead of the first draft of the simulations' results released in October 2024, the ZeroW Policy Team re-engaged the external stakeholders who participated in the three WGs of T8.1 and reached out to additional ones of relevance to the ZeroW objectives. 20 stakeholders expressed interest in joining or staying informed about the project outcomes. Following the release of the simulations' results in

⁴ For the four food commodities of the Partial Equilibrium Model (chicken, fruit, bread, and milk), the largest share of the data is from the United Kingdom in 2012; however, data from other European countries or years were used when the necessary data was not available in the United Kingdom (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025). For the MAGNET analysis, the model database is the Global Trade Analysis (GTAP) database version 11 (Aguiar et al., 2023; Bartelings and Gatto, 2025).

October 2024, the team reviewed them and organised two roundtables with stakeholders from across the FSC to gather further feedback.

In these roundtables, the ZeroW Policy Team presented and analysed the FLW modelling results. Two sessions were organised and held online⁵. The participants were provided with background material and guiding questions tailored to the **key findings** and impact areas from the results, so that they could provide the Policy team with direct validation of the results and offer additional feedback (see Annex II). The first session focused specifically on collecting the stakeholders' validation of the key findings and their implications, especially on the feasibility of the reduction targets, while the second session deepened the discussions towards effective policy design and strategies, highlighting social impacts and the need for collaboration and partnerships. Their validation and feedback on the simulations were collected during the roundtables in collaboration with the colleagues from the WUR who participated to introduce the results and answer questions from the stakeholders.⁶ This process allowed both the WP1 team and the WP8 team to enrich and revise the modelling results, which are now available in D1.3. Additional feedback from a stakeholder in the fishing sector was gathered through a written questionnaire.

In Chapter 6, we lay out and implement the combination of these two approaches. For each policy pathway and related scenario, we provide the suggested targets and the considerations from the modelling results, underlying how just and realistic they are and integrating them directly with our conceptual framework and 'just pathway' definition, as well as with the validation and feedback from the external stakeholders. Through this analysis, we identify key actions and interventions that need to be pursued within a potential 'just' pathway, and fundamental trade-offs that cannot be ignored. Crucially, we attain a detailed overview and comparison of the targets from each pathway, allowing for a balanced selection of the 'just and realistic intermediate targets' that best align with these specific actions. It is imperative to note that we provide a proposal that serves as guidance for policymaking, since the analysis shows that the choice of setting just and realistic intermediate targets should not be without careful consideration for key trade-offs and the need for tailored interventions. For this reason, our chosen target percentages should be viewed as an **approximation** derived from a **balanced assessment of the simulations, the conceptual framework, and stakeholder feedback**. Additionally, we aim to address the concerns on their feasibility by providing potential integrations with the SILLs currently being

⁵ of 1.5 hours each, the first on November 28 and the second on December 4, 2024.

⁶ The anonymity of stakeholders is upheld throughout the deliverable to safeguard their privacy when sharing insights during the roundtables. However, a list of participating organisations and companies is available in Annex III for reference.

developed by the ZeroW project (see section 6.3). This process lays the foundation towards the work of the next task (T8.3), identifying areas where more specific policy interventions and recommendations will be required in the short and medium term. The identified 'Just Pathway Actions' in the next chapter serve as a starting point for this objective.

6. Setting just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets towards 2050

6.1 The requirements of the F2F Action Plan

The *Farm-to-Fork (F2F) Action Plan* and its specific requirements serve as the main reference for setting fair and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets in this deliverable.

As a key component of the *European Green Deal*, the European Commission's *F2F Strategy* aims to establish a fair, healthy, and environmentally sustainable food system. Central to this goal is the proposal to set legally binding EU-level targets for FW reduction, which the Commission recommended as part of the revision of the WFD, adopted on 5 July 2023. This proposal is vital to accelerate the EU's progress towards SDG Target 12.3 (European Commission, 2023b). To measure the MS progress, the revision uses data from the first EU-wide monitoring of FW levels conducted in 2020 as a baseline. Specifically, MS would be required to take the necessary measures to reduce FW by the end of 2030:

- Primary production – no target;
- by 10%, in processing and manufacturing;
- by 30% (per capita), jointly at retail and consumption (restaurants, food services and households).

This legislative proposal ensures that MS progress will be formally reviewed by the end of 2027. Subsequently, the Commission will assess whether the targets should be adjusted, if evidence indicates that the EU could further contribute to SDG 12.3. The proposal is supported by the JRC Impact Assessment that gathered data on FW prevention activities and analysed the environmental, economic, and social impacts of different target levels (European Commission, 2023b; Joint Research Center, 2023).

In March 2024, the Parliament adopted its position on the Directive⁷. The following targets were agreed:

- 20% reduction in FW from processing and manufacturing by 2030 (increased from 10% in Commission's original proposal).
- 40% reduction in FW per capita in retail, restaurants, food services and households by 2030 (increased from 10% in Commission's original proposal).

Primary production remains exempt from the targets in the Parliament's position. However, the Parliament decided that the Commission should carry out an evaluation by December 2027 to determine whether primary production should be

⁷ with 514 votes in favour, 20 against and 91 abstentions.

incorporated into the reduction targets. Additionally, they should assess the possibility of increasing the target for processing and manufacturing to 30% and raising the target for retail, restaurants, food services, and households to 50% (European Parliament, 2024).

In June 2024, the Council reached a compromise on the Directive, adopting its position of 'general approach', which maintains the same FW reduction targets for 2030 as originally set by the Commission. In this agreement, MS were given the flexibility to choose the reference year among 2021, 2022, and 2023 for setting targets. However, the Commission would still be obligated to submit its report on FLW in the primary production sector by December 2027, potentially alongside a legislative proposal (Council of the European Union, 2024).

Lastly, the WFD trilogue negotiations between the Commission, the Parliament, and the Council reached a conclusion on 19 February 2025 with a provisional agreement between the co-legislators. The Council and the European Parliament agreed to introduce **world-first binding food waste reduction targets** to be met at the national level by 31 December 2030, with the percentage values corresponding to the **original EC proposal** (European Commission, 2025). In the next section, we utilise these targets as a benchmark for our final proposal.

6.2 Drawing from the modelling results and stakeholders' roundtables: Setting the targets

In this section, we draw from both the modelling results and the feedback from the external stakeholders gathered during the roundtables to assess the feasibility and key considerations of the FLW reduction targets for each policy pathway. This analysis is conducted in relation to the requirements of the *F2F Action Plan* and incorporates the theoretical assessment of the core elements of a 'just pathway' and the way forward towards its achievement.

Based on this analysis, several intermediate targets were carefully selected and evaluated, ultimately proposing those deemed most fair and realistic for the 2050 horizon. The final selection is supported by a thorough assessment of key considerations for each policy pathway scenario, including trade-offs, quantitative simulations data, and stakeholders' insights. The following paragraphs delve into these considerations in detail.

Policy Pathway 1: "Green Growth" (Market-Driven)

This scenario takes a pragmatic, market-driven approach to policies, acknowledging the slow progress toward SDG 12.3 (Stroodsnijder et al., 2023). It establishes legally binding targets across the FSC, complemented by ambitious voluntary agreements. By 2032, this pathway sets the following FW reduction targets (see table 4 for further details):

- **Processing & Manufacturing:** 10% mandatory, 25% voluntary FLW reduction.
- **Retail & Consumption:** 30% mandatory (per capita), 50% voluntary FLW reduction.

These targets **align with the EC proposal** to revise the WFD. This scenario incorporates ambitious voluntary targets consistent with SDG 12.3, aiming to stimulate private sector actions (Goossens et al., 2019). Modelling results suggest that achieving these targets would require a significant increase in FLW disposal taxes. For instance, the tax on consumer-level FW for chicken would need to rise by nearly 5000%. This finding indicates that market-driven approaches alone, or heavy taxation measures on FW disposal, may be **politically unfeasible**, given the likely difficulty in securing support, and **practically challenging** due to the high enforcement costs. Consequently, such approaches may be insufficient to meet the targets and achieve the intended objectives. P1 focuses on increasing the cost of producing FW associated with food at home (FAH) consumption. This approach focuses on reducing household generated FW, which accounts for the largest share of total FW produced within the FSC. The cost of FAH increases as consumers face higher disposal costs for their FW, prompting greater efforts to abate FW at home. As the model simulations demonstrate, consumers partially shift to FAFH, while the overall food consumption declines. For instance, in this pathway, a reduction in consumer FAH is observed with a 18% decrease for chicken and 21% for fruit (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025). The MAGNET analysis shows that in P1, introducing direct taxation on FLW at various stages, combined with voluntary reductions, results in a cumulative FLW reduction of -62.1% by 2030. This is primarily driven by a reduction in household consumption (-80%; Pijpers and Drabik, 2025). Like in P2, the decrease in FAH consumption, even if partially offset by increased eating out (FAFH), raises concerns about food accessibility, especially for commodities like fruits.

In line with the core principles of justice and our definition of a just pathway, any measures to reduce FLW generation (e.g. more ambitious reduction targets) should not burden vulnerable consumers who are often price-sensitive and may struggle to afford nutritious foods like fruits in this scenario. To ensure a 'just' transition, food policies must prioritise access to nutritious food, an aspect often overlooked as food is treated as a mere 'commodity' rather than as a 'good' (see Section 4.1.1). If higher reduction targets disproportionately impact low-income households, the policy goals may become counterproductive and unfair. Moreover, there is the risk that consumers may increase their reliance on processed and lower-quality foods (Section 4.2.1).

High disposal taxes could disproportionately affect small retailers and restaurants, which are more vulnerable than larger companies that have the resources to invest in waste reduction technologies. Simulations suggest that increased disposal costs may result in a shift of FLW to sectors not subject to the tax, such as processing for fruit and bread in P1 (see figure 9 below). As a result, these sectors could experience higher edible FLW rates, as their disposal costs decrease after taxing other stages in the supply chain (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025). Furthermore, it is vital to acknowledge that consumer behaviour changes slowly and is influenced by multiple socio-economic factors that must be considered. During the roundtable discussions on voluntary targets, stakeholders emphasised that while technological innovations help tackle food system challenges and reduce abatement costs, fostering a **mindset change** is just as crucial. The discussions emphasised that a significant driver of FLW is the perception among some consumers that food is easily disposable with little immediate cost to wasting it. The simulations show that increased production efficiency through FLW reduction generally lowers food prices across the supply chain. However, this price decrease may inadvertently reinforce the perception of food as less valuable, potentially making waste more acceptable.

Cultural norms and social behaviours surrounding food disposal thus play a pivotal role and require intervention beyond technological solutions – specifically, social and cultural innovations aimed at transforming deeply ingrained attitudes. Policymakers should prioritise reshaping perceptions of food from being seen as a disposable commodity to a valuable good (see Section 4.1.1). This shift is critical for influencing both market dynamics and driving sustainable social behaviours. Additionally, practical approaches to encourage behavioural changes are needed to sustain stakeholders' interest and engagement. Without them, there is a risk of waning commitment, which could undermine broader goals. Addressing these cultural and behavioural dimensions is vital for achieving a fair transition and fostering a truly holistic transformation of our food system.

% Change in the edible FLW rate of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Post-harvest farmer	24.8	10.4	18.4	17.5
THS	24.5	9.9	18.1	16.7
Processor	-4.3	9.1	4.7	-5.4
Retailer	-9.3	-7.6	-13.8	-25.6
HRI	9.0	7.2	5.2	10.7
Consumer FAFH	21.7	62.2	58.1	37.8
Consumer FAH	-24.1	-23.1	-15.6	-26.7
Policy pathway 2				
Post-harvest farmer	-56.3	-40.2	-67.9	-53.1
THS	-56.1	-39.2	-67.6	-52.1
Processor	-52.2	-38.1	-53.0	-48.2
Retailer	-44.1	-35.9	-37.2	-43.7
HRI	-45.9	-35.4	-38.4	-45.4
Consumer FAFH	-87.2	-81.8	-79.8	-75.0
Consumer FAH	-29.8	-29.4	-24.1	-40.6
Policy pathway 3				
Post-harvest farmer	6.5	4.6	9.1	7.5
THS	6.4	4.4	8.9	7.2
Processor	5.4	4.1	4.5	5.9
Retailer	-18.5	-14.0	-11.3	-14.1
HRI	3.9	3.3	2.6	4.9
Consumer FAFH	8.0	25.2	23.8	15.9
Consumer FAH	-10.4	-10.6	-6.1	-12.5

Figure 9: Changes in edible FLW rates along the supply chain for different policy pathways (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)

Pathway 2: "Sustainability First" – Government-Driven Approach

P2 presents a clear shift in structural governance, characterised by a top-down approach to FW reduction, mandatory reporting mechanisms and penalties for non-compliance, and highly ambitious reduction targets (D'haese et al., 2023):

- **All Stages:** 50% FLW reduction by 2030; Near-100% reduction by 2050 (see table 5).

These targets **far exceed the EC proposal** to revise the WFD, aiming for a uniformly applied 50% reduction target across all stages of the FSC - from primary production to consumption - while reducing reliance on voluntary agreements.

To achieve these ambitious and uniformly applied FLW reduction goals, which emphasise sustainability in the EU future governance, the simulations indicate that substantial increases in disposal costs are required. For chicken, a 6101% increase in disposal costs is necessary at each stage of the supply chain. In contrast, milk reaches the targets with significantly lower taxes – 1488% (see figure

10 below and D1.3 for more details). This is due to the significant impact of inedible FLW – commodities like milk, which produce no inedible FLW, can meet total FLW reduction targets at lower costs compared to commodities like chicken, which generate substantial inedible FLW (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025).

Required % change in the unit cost of disposal for the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer	-32.8	-62.2	-60.1	-47.6
THS	-32.8	-62.2	-60.1	-47.6
Processor	537.2	-62.2	-15.1	124.9
Retailer	1017.2	537.8	579.9	582.4
HRI	-32.8	-62.2	-60.1	-47.6
Consumer	4967.2	2137.8	1369.9	712.4
Policy pathway 2				
Farmer	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
THS	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
Processor	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
Retailer	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
HRI	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
Consumer	6101.4	2956.1	2347.1	1488.3
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-14.5	-36.4	-34.8	-25.8
THS	-14.5	-36.4	-34.8	-25.8
Processor	-14.5	-36.4	-34.8	-25.8
Retailer	1585.5	743.6	425.2	255.2
HRI	-14.5	-36.4	-34.8	-25.8
Consumer	1585.5	743.6	425.2	255.2

Figure 10: Required % change in disposal costs along the supply chain for different policy pathways (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)

Stakeholders partaking in our roundtables generally agreed that, although the targets seem realistic, implementing such high taxation would be highly challenging. Global geopolitics factors further complicate matters - trade tensions between the United States and China, along with shifting priorities under the new United States Trump administration, may lead to changes in environmental and agricultural policies that hinder efforts to reduce FW and achieve global environmental goals.

The MAGNET analysis highlights that achieving a 90% FLW reduction by 2050 would demand significantly higher taxes - possibly up to 110% - to drive the necessary behavioural and operational changes (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025). Successful taxation measures demand strict enforcement to enforce mandatory compliance. However, these findings raise serious concerns about the feasibility of these targets. As one stakeholder pointed out, excessive taxation could prompt

economic actors to resist or circumvent regulations, potentially leading to harmful outcomes such as illegal dumping, or reliance on less preferred solutions in the Food Waste Hierarchy, such as composting.

The simulations reveal mixed effects on food prices: producer prices rise for chicken (10.7%) but decline for fruit and bread. Most notably, this pathway shows a significant shift toward FAFH, with FAH consumption dropping by 35% and total food consumption decreasing by up to 30% for fruits (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025). This consumption shift is even more concerning than in P1, indicating that higher taxation may not only be economically unfeasible but could also have unintended consequences on vulnerable consumers, undermining their right to affordable healthy food. Such outcomes directly contradict the definition of a just pathway, which, as outlined in Chapter 4, requires that benefits and responsibilities of interventions be equitably shared among all stakeholders, with particular attention to **pre-existing vulnerabilities** within the FSC.

A public sector representative at the roundtables noted that uniform taxation across all supply chain stages would disproportionately burden its most vulnerable segments. To mitigate this, stakeholders proposed a tax reduction strategy that balances economic incentives with regulatory enforcement. However, they highlighted how governments often lack the political will to implement such frameworks effectively – though doing so could be a crucial first step toward achieving the reduction targets.

While stakeholders appreciated this pathway's sustainability focus, they criticised its 'one-size-fits-all' taxation approach for overlooking the varying capacities of actors – particularly small producers and informal retailers - to bear costs. Strict enforcement and monitoring that are essential to prevent fraud pose further implementation challenges (see Section 4.2.4). Small retailers and processors may face high administrative burden, while larger corporations could absorb costs, potentially leading to market consolidation and monopolisation. The simulations highlight cascading supply chain effects: uneven enforcement may even increase FLW rates upstream and downstream (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025).

One retailer also warned that an overemphasis on indicators like 'volume reduction' risks a superficial solution that ignores underlying environmental issues. Prioritising waste revalorisation could prevent the need for higher FLW disposal taxes. A public sector representative echoed this, emphasising that preventing food waste at its source is more effective than focusing on disposal. Similarly, a Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) representative stressed targeting FSC stages with inadequate prevention through tailored taxes and incentives.

Including primary production in this pathway contributes to its perception of unfeasibility. A representative from primary production argued that mandatory

reductions for this sector overlook unpredictable factors like weather variability and market demand shocks that could unfairly penalise producers. Climate change is closely tied to these unpredictable weather factors, such as droughts, floods, pests, and biodiversity loss, all of which exacerbate existing inequalities and perpetuate socio-economic disparities (see Section 4.1.2). Without cost-sharing across the value chain, taxation could deepen these disparities. Stakeholders recommend stage-specific interventions, as FLW causes and reduction opportunities vary.

In primary production, voluntary measures focusing on interventions at critical points (e.g., incentivising surplus redistribution) may be more effective. Suggested solutions include incentives that support connections between primary producers and food banks to fund activities like gleanings or transporting surplus to people in need, which are usually too costly for producers to undertake due to financial and logistical constraints (e.g. lack of facilities, or time). Stricter FLW reporting requirements, however, risk discouraging donations due to compliance burden, food safety concerns, and reputational risks. Tax incentives, legal protection for donors (e.g. Good Samaritan laws) and streamlined bureaucracy could mitigate these issues. Notably, Catalonia's Food Loss and Waste Prevention Law provides a model for successful company-food bank partnership (Zero Waste Europe, 2021).

Pathway 3: "Innovation First" – Voluntary and Technological Approach

P3 provides an alternative scenario that prioritises a collaborative, bottom-up approach involving all FSC actors and relying on innovation and technology integration as the key drivers for FLW reduction. Accordingly, its targets reflect ambitious voluntary agreements for FSC actors leveraging a market-driven framework, as can be seen in table 6 and outlined below (D'haese et al., 2023):

- **Primary Production:** 10% voluntary FLW reduction by 2030, 50% voluntary by 2050.
- **Processing & Manufacturing:** 50% voluntary FLW reduction by 2030, 100% voluntary by 2050.
- **Retail & Consumption:** 15% mandatory, 50% voluntary FLW reduction by 2030, 100% voluntary by 2050.

These targets **fall short of the EC proposal** to revise the WFD, as they include only a single mandatory target of a 15% per capita reduction in retail and consumption by 2030. P3 places greater emphasis on voluntary targets that are intended to foster growth and innovation by focusing on technological advancements and their integration in the market. However, modelling results show that achieving the voluntary targets of Policy P1 and, especially in Policy P3 in 2030, would require a significant reduction in abatement costs (i.e. the expenses incurred by FSC actors to reduce FLW) to be feasible. In fact, these targets are not attainable for chicken and fruits under the current cost conditions (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025).

% Change in the quantity of FLW of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer pre-harvest	7.1	-0.1	0.1	5.4
Farmer post-harvest	9.2	1.7	20.2	14.0
THS	8.4	0.7	19.3	12.9
Processor	-25.0	-25.0	-25.0	-24.9
Retail	-50.0	-50.0	-50.0	-50.1
HRI	5.9	5.4	-0.2	12.9
FAFH	36.6	47.9	127.6	99.8
FAH	-40.5	-32.7	-50.0	-50.1
Retail + FAH	-42.2	-35.6	-50.0	-50.1
Total post-harvest supply chain	-17.4	-27.0	-31.6	-26.8
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer pre-harvest	3.2	0.4	-0.3	-6.2
Farmer post-harvest	-10.0	-10.1	-10.1	-10.0
THS	7.4	15.4	24.2	11.1
Processor	-49.6	-48.7	-49.9	-50.0
Retail	-97.0	-96.8	-58.7	-52.5
HRI	5.4	3.0	-2.6	4.8
FAFH	51.4	53.3	153.8	121.6
FAH	-32.9	-23.2	-45.2	-48.3
Retail + FAH	-44.3	-35.6	-50.1	-50.0
Total post-harvest supply chain	-24.0	-30.1	-35.3	-31.7

Note: Red-shaded cells indicate a policy objective was not achieved in the simulations. Green-shaded cells indicate that the policy objective was achieved in the simulation.

Figure 11: Changes in the total quantity of FLW for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030 (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)

Pijpers and Drabik (2025) clarify that, from an economic perspective, the effectiveness of a voluntary agreement for FLW reduction is questionable. The general assumption is that any such agreement requires supply chain actors to invest in developing new FLW reducing technologies. These investments are necessary, as they lower the abatement costs, enabling actors to meet voluntary FLW targets, **while still increasing their profits**. This applies equally to the consumer at home – where it is assumed that public investments are necessary to develop new FW reducing technologies for use at home. As mentioned in section 3.1.2, the extent to which abatement costs must be reduced to achieve voluntary targets serves as an indicator of their feasibility: the greater the required reduction, the less likely the target will be met. A significant issue with P3 is that its voluntary targets require **massive technological advancements** to reduce abatement costs by 99.9% in certain sectors like retail (see figure 12 below).

Required % shift of the abatement costs of the	Chicken	Fruit	Bread	Milk
Policy pathway 1				
Farmer	0	0	0	0
THS	0	0	0	0
Processor	-65.0	-69.8	-72.3	-32.7
Retailer	-66.6	-67.8	-69.0	-53.5
HRI	0	0	0	0
Consumer	-99.9	-99.9	-77.5	-57.0
Policy pathway 3				
Farmer	-29.5	-36.0	-47.7	-34.6
THS	0	0	0	0
Processor	-99.9	-99.9	-99.9	-79.2
Retailer	-99.9	-99.9	-83.9	-72.5
HRI	0	0	0	0
Consumer	-99.9	-99.9	-83.9	-72.5

Figure 12: Required % shift of the abatement costs for the mandatory + voluntary targets in 2030 (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025)

Achieving this goal is challenging without groundbreaking technological and social innovations, coupled with large-scale public-private investments to make such a sharp decrease feasible. However, several critical aspects of technological innovations must be considered. Developing scalable, cost-effective solutions that are sustainable in the long-term is notoriously difficult. For instance, innovative packaging for fresh fish - a key focus of the ZeroW SILL2 - illustrates these challenges. When presenting this idea, one of the retailers in the roundtables highlighted not only how such an innovation would represent a solution merely for a small fraction of the products their company sells, but also that price still remains a crucial factor to consider - even highly efficient technologies that significantly extend a product's shelf life will not be adopted if the costs are too high. Additionally, retailers face challenges such as food neophobia and technophobia, which can hinder the acceptance of innovations aimed at reducing waste (see Section 4.1.2). These barriers are significant, as they not only limit the adoption of new technologies but also complicate efforts to scale up solutions that could otherwise help address sustainability and waste reduction. Only if the innovation is scalable, as production of the technological innovation increases, economies of scale would lead to lower costs, making its implementation more financially feasible. Other existing innovations that are promising but not yet scalable for all businesses include AI-driven inventory tracking and upcycled food products. The stakeholder added that regulatory changes, such as banning single-use plastics, are highly effective in easing the adoption of such innovations because they leave no

alternative other than adapting. Thus, funding for financial viability must increase or changes need to be mandated through regulation. Another retailer concurred that price drives market behaviour and unsustainable production must not be allowed to remain the cheaper option, as this resembles the key obstacle to market transformation. They added that while subsidies currently exist to encourage companies to adopt sustainable practices, many businesses (especially SMEs) struggle to access them, burdened by administrative complexities and lack of awareness. For instance, SMEs typically lack the specialised resources, teams, or technical expertise needed to navigate subsidy applications. A crucial action to make the transition more just should allow to explore ways to make these funds more accessible to all actors, through effective dissemination channels, and not only to large companies that can afford dedicated expert teams (see Section 4.2.3).

As expected, this pathway results in a lower FLW Disposal Tax for Retail and Consumption compared to P1 and P2, especially for milk. However, taxes still need to increase by 255% for retail and consumption, which raises similar concerns about taxation measures discussed earlier (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025). Additionally, simulations of the voluntary agreements reveal the uncertainty regarding FLW reductions on their impact on prices. In some cases, prices rise very quickly due to the voluntary targets. In this pathway the initial reduction from the mandatory targets is completely offset. For instance, all prices for milk along the supply chain, except at retail, increase. Importantly, the results for voluntary targets indicate that the supply chain stages without FLW reduction targets see an increase in FLW quantities compared to mandatory targets. The FW generated by FAFH consumption more than doubles for bread and milk in P1 and P3 compared to the baseline (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025).

Although this pathway might mitigate some of the negative unintended consequences of high taxation measures, a fully market-driven FLW reduction still poses challenges and affects vulnerable actors. For example, small-scale farmers and producers may lack access to new technologies, putting them at a competitive disadvantage within the value chain (see Section 4.1.4). Moreover, if innovation becomes the main driver of FLW reduction, for example through the introduction of more automation and AI technologies, workers in manual food handling roles (e.g., packaging, sorting, restaurant staff) may face significant job losses that would cast doubts on the 'just' aspect of this pathway. If inequalities cannot be addressed and the transition cannot be fully inclusive, this should be acknowledged in line with the recognition criterion of our definition of a just pathway (see section 4.1.3). Compensation for these vulnerable groups should also be planned ex-ante when devising policies. The primary role of innovation cannot overshadow the importance of considering the digital divide in the food system – the high costs and complexity of innovative digital tools may exclude lower-income producers and consumers alike

(see section 4.1.4). Disparities arising from differences in education, attitudes toward innovation and other psychological and socio-demographic factors must be addressed to ensure a just pathway. In addition, the use of digital tools can create a 'trolley dilemma', requiring a balance between the benefits of increased food production and the potential unintended consequences for marginalised groups and environmental sustainability (see section 4.1.4). Lastly, overreliance on voluntary agreements may hinder FLW reduction progress in line with SDG 12.3, as low participation may delay its advancement. This concern was noted by a retailer during the roundtables, who argued that a purely voluntary approach is unlikely to motivate retailers to address FLW reduction, especially given the limited progress observed in some MS lacking strategic plans. Moreover, the simulations' results underline the pivotal role of inedible FLW (see section 3.2). Even with technological innovations that lower the abatement costs of edible FLW, the overall impact on FLW reduction would remain limited for commodities with high inedible waste rates, such as household chicken waste (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025).

Final considerations: Our proposal for just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets

Before delving into our proposal for FLW reduction targets, it is imperative to link back to the MAGNET analysis' results, which showcase some of the critical unintended spillover effects across the pathways (see section 3.2). While FLW reduction policies are projected to lead to substantial GHG emissions reductions in waste treatment and collection (particularly in P1 by 2030 – where emissions drop by 7 million tons of CO₂-equivalents), emissions are expected to increase in primary agriculture and non-food sectors across all scenarios. This is a consequence of the rise in non-food demand linked to lower food prices and higher food affordability driven by FLW reductions (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025). Emissions from non-food sectors rise from 1 million tons of CO₂-equivalents under P2 to 1.5 million tons under P1, where the combined impact of voluntary reductions and taxes leads to a comparatively greater rise in non-food demand. By 2050, this rise is actually more contained in P2, as taxes affect consumer budgets and limit the rise in non-food demand, compared to P3 where the reliance on voluntary reductions leads to the highest increase of non-food emissions, primarily from textiles, manufacturing, and energy sectors that account for 80% of the increased emissions (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025). Additionally, as already pointed out in section 3.1, these growing emissions from non-food sectors are overall not offset by the reductions achieved in waste treatment, driving this 'rebound effect' to the frontstage of the policymaking discussion. These results show that the proposed pathways may end up being less 'environmentally sustainable' than they are meant to be. In other words, 'sustainability first' in one sector of the economy (i.e. FLW reduction) *does not translate* into 'sustainability first' in the overall economy. If the overall outcome is an

increase in GHG emissions with serious environmental consequences, one of the goals of FLW reduction is undermined. This risk is evident in scenarios where significantly higher taxation is applied to one segment of the FSC without considering others, as well as approaches that rely primarily on voluntary agreements. Thus, it would be advisable to prioritise other approaches besides waste treatment, such as waste prevention at the source, which several stakeholders have pointed out to be crucial - i.e. requiring **greater consideration** when devising policies at the EU level.

Figure 13: Change (million tons of CO₂-equivalents) in greenhouse gas emissions by source in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050 (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025)

Figure 14: Change (million tons of CO₂-equivalents) in greenhouse gas emissions by country in the EU27 across investigated scenarios with respect to the Business-as-usual (BAU) baseline scenario in 2030 and 2050.

Since one of the main goals of reducing FLW is to lessen the environmental footprint of our food system, the ZeroW Policy Team seeks to highlight potential unintended consequences associated with more ambitious FLW reduction targets. Drawing from concerns raised during the roundtables regarding primary production, and the findings from the simulations, it is evident that the environmental footprint of FLW varies throughout the value chain. FLW at the primary production stage has a significantly lower environmental impact compared to the same product wasted at the final stages of the supply chain, which include the additional environmental costs from processing, transportation, and distribution. Consequently, reducing FLW at the final stages is far more effective and sustainable than focusing primarily on early-stage reductions.

Given the redistribution effect of FLW across the value chain, taxation policies should be designed to prioritise waste reduction at the final stages, rather than earlier stages. It is crucial that tax schemes do not unintentionally shift FLW from primary production to final consumption, as this could lead to more environmental damage instead of less. Moreover, results from the Partial Equilibrium Model highlight that different taxation rates affect different stages of the value chain differently, reinforcing the **need for a differentiated taxation approach** rather than a uniform tax across all stages. A fixed tax rate that only considers environmental factors would fail to account for these dynamics and could lead to unintended waste redistribution. This rationale is also particularly relevant for P1,

where balancing voluntary reductions with targeted taxation is crucial to ensuring effective and fair FLW mitigation along the value chain.

All things considered, the analysis and interpretation of the simulations' results, integrated with direct validation and feedback from stakeholders and with our conceptual framework of a just pathway, reveal that **crucial trade-offs exist** and must be considered when selecting just and realistic FLW reduction targets. These trade-offs also impact consumers, highlighting important concerns about food accessibility that must be carefully evaluated. In line with the principles of a just pathway, it is essential to ensure that taxation measures or any other approach are **equitably distributed across the FSC, preventing disproportionate burdens on consumers**. Each pathway involves balancing economic feasibility, regulatory enforcement, and market-driven solutions. These trade-offs become even more significant from a macroeconomic perspective, as substantial FLW reductions may still negatively impact the overall economic sustainability. As Bartelings and Gatto (2025) suggest, a **hybrid strategy** could be advisable, blending moderate taxation, strong incentives and subsidies for innovation, and targeted voluntary agreements, tailored to the specific conditions of each country and FSC stage. This hybrid strategy seems to be the best fit for achieving the goals of a just pathway.

Therefore, our proposal for just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets for 2030 – ultimately aiming for near-zero waste by 2050, builds on a more balanced combination of the targets from scenarios P1 and P3, with a focus on mitigating **negative spillovers and addressing concerns**. Our analysis clearly shows that P2 is overly ambitious, with negative repercussions and environmental spillovers that render its proposed targets neither just nor feasible by 2030.

Food waste reduction target on	Mandatory 2030 FW reduction target	Voluntary 2030 FW reduction target
Primary production	n/a	10%
Processing & Manufacturing	10% (absolute amount in mass units)	For higher target levels
Retail & Consumption	30% (per capita)	For higher target levels

Table 7: Final proposal for just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets (2030)

As emphasised earlier, the primary focus for FLW reduction should be on the later stages of the FSC, leaving primary production without a mandatory target. Given the reallocation effect of FLW along the FSC based on the characteristics of each stage, taxation measures should aim at decreasing the most FW at the later stages. A

taxation scheme that shifts FLW from earlier to later stages (e.g., from primary production to final consumption) would ignore the importance of this reallocation effect. Fixed taxation is problematic, even when considering ‘environmental parameters’, as shown by the MAGNET analysis, and its potential lack of enforcement could lead to further imbalances across the FSC. However, a voluntary target of 10% could still be useful in sparking collaborative partnerships across the FSC and incentivise further support for innovations.

Regarding voluntary targets for the other stages, it is generally advisable to aim for higher levels than those set by mandatory targets. However, the analysis indicates that achieving the voluntary targets of P3 would require massive technological advancements, making them most likely unfeasible by 2030 without considerable investments and subsidies towards FLW-reducing new technologies. Innovations, including those currently being tested in the ZeroW SILLs (see the ‘Just Pathway Actions’ below) could play a critical role in bridging this gap. Thus, voluntary targets serve as a motivating factor towards these interventions.

The remaining targets align with the EC proposal. This is a rather **indicative** choice to balance the simulation results with the need to achieve the requirements of the *F2F Action Plan*. While simulations of the 30% mandatory reduction target for retail and consumption indicate that the increase of the FW disposal tax would remain significantly high, this approach represents a compromise to mitigate some of the identified negative consequences while still ensuring a positive impact and meaningful reduction. Avoiding extreme taxation is as necessary as preventing excessive reliance on voluntary targets, which could hinder progress. Moderate mandatory targets also function as a motivating factor, increasing the FSC stages’ efforts towards addressing FLW reduction and avoiding stagnation or slow progress. Alternatively, EU policymakers could re-evaluate whether binding FLW reduction targets make sense and consider shifting the focus onto different, potentially more effective approaches such as waste revalorisation, as was reiterated by several stakeholders during the roundtables.

Furthermore, the simulations’ results and our analysis highlight that these targets can only be met or approached by 2030 **through the implementation of the following 7 key actions and interventions**. These are necessary for the targets’ success and derive directly from the analysis of the combination of the different trade-offs and potential unintended consequences that have been identified. It is important to note that this list may also be non-exhaustive, based on the limitations of the modelling simulations. Further research in some identified respects is recommended. We label these identified potential actions and interventions ‘Just Pathway Actions’, representing the key actions to undertake and pursue to achieve a ‘just’ pathway (i.e. corresponding to the developed conceptual

framework and addressing the simulations’ results and stakeholder feedback). This pathway would be necessarily **hybrid** in nature - there is no straightforward, one-size-fits-all approach that can ignore the identified trade-offs and concerns. The need for tailored strategies should not be ignored by policymakers. These actions are presented in detail in the next section. Following the recent EU adoption of the first-ever FW reduction targets, MS urgently need to develop action plans to meet them. The results of the pathways’ simulations, along with this deliverable, **can inform the strategy and design** of these plans by highlighting key insights and actionable recommendations that are highly valuable for policymakers.

6.3 Towards specific policy recommendations: Integrations with the ZeroW SILLs

This section presents the ‘Just Pathway Actions’ and sets the stage for more specific policy interventions, prioritising integrations with the work being carried out by the ZeroW SILLs. On 5 February 2025, the ZeroW Policy Team organised an internal workshop with colleagues from WP6 and WP1, to conduct a matching exercise between ‘Just Pathway Actions’ and the progress of the innovations currently being developed and tested in the ZeroW SILLs, to identify where and how the SILLs could contribute to achieving the just pathway and intermediate targets in the future (see Annex IV). The team also identified key challenges frequently faced by the SILLs, further underscoring the critical importance of implementing the Just Pathway Actions.

Figure 15: Overview of the ZeroW SILLs

Figure 16: Overview of the Just Pathway Actions

Action 1: Differentiated FLW reduction targets across countries, actors and commodities

The proposed targets should be differentiated across countries, actors within the FSC, and commodities rather than adopting a uniform taxation. The MAGNET analysis (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025) reveals significant disparities in FW levels, economic impacts, and environmental outcomes across countries, actors and commodities. These variations stem from varying consumption patterns, agricultural structures, and waste management practices. To ensure both fairness and effectiveness in reducing food waste, policies should be tailored to **national contexts**. As MS will now be required to devise action plans to meet the approved EU FW reduction targets by 2030 (see section 6.1), the MAGNET analysis and the recommendations from Bartelings and Gatto (2025) offer crucial insights (see section 3.2). The Distribution, Retail, and Consumption stages are the main sources of FLW in the EU27, making them key targets for policy interventions aimed at achieving substantial waste reductions by 2030 and 2050. A tax-based approach for higher-income, capital-intensive agricultural sectors in northern Europe could target these stages most effectively. Additionally, wealthier consumers are more responsive to price changes, making taxation an effective tool to reduce spillovers into non-food demand sectors and lower emissions. In contrast, southern European countries with labour-intensive agriculture should prioritise voluntary FLW reduction measures to support socio-economic growth, job creation, and production efficiency. Modest tax-based incentives could complement these efforts, encouraging efficiency without imposing high costs (Bartelings and Gatto, 2025).

Similarly, findings from the Partial Equilibrium Model analysis demonstrate that varying taxation rates have distinct impact across the value chain, highlighting

the risk of waste redistribution. While the FLW reduction targets are already sector-specific, their implementation should account for the financial and operational capabilities of **actors within supply chain stages**. For instance, insights from SILL3 (*Wasteless Greenhouse Solutions for the pre-harvest & harvest stages*) reinforce the importance of addressing structural limitations of actors, such as limited electricity access for certain primary producers, that must be considered. In practice, policymakers could establish customised reduction benchmarks, differentiating between larger corporations and small businesses. Depending on their capabilities, businesses could be subject to voluntary or mandatory FLW reporting requirements, enabling them to set reasonable, fair and achievable reduction goals. Similar tailored interventions would prevent the overburdening of smaller, vulnerable companies and the most negative spillovers associated with taxation measures. As showcased by the Partial Equilibrium Model, a disposal tax may disproportionately impact lower-income households by increasing food disposal costs for FAH, potentially reducing access to essential and healthy food like fruits (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025).

An even more specific implementation could consist of a graduated, progressive tax system on FW disposal, where larger businesses and higher-income households face higher disposal tax rates compared to smaller entities that receive instead exemptions or lower rates. The tiered tax brackets could be based on business revenue, waste volume (assuming increased efforts and investment in FLW monitoring and quantification), or sector. The graduated waste disposal fees would then be based on business size and industry. Progressive FLW taxation models may also better address the need to tailor policy instruments to the specific FSC stages more effectively, as identified in the latest OECD report analysing global FLW policy environments. Current policy instruments lack clarity (OECD, 2025). As discussed in the roundtables, positive incentives could prove more useful in aiding these efforts. For instance, compliance incentives, such as tax reductions for proven waste-reduction strategies (e.g., donation, redistribution) could encourage larger food producers and retailers to adopt more effective waste-reduction strategies. Examples include waivers or tax breaks for those businesses that demonstrate significant waste reduction. However, these measures would require mandatory FLW tracking to ensure compliance and fairness. In such a context, peer learning and knowledge sharing should be encouraged among businesses, strengthening partnerships across the FSC and ensuring accountability as well as transparency from all actors (Mesiranta et al. 2022; Section 4.3.2).

In addition to country and actor specific policies, FLW reduction targets should also account for the **characteristics of different food categories**, particularly plant-based commodities such as cereals, grains and horticultural products, which constitute the largest share of FLW in the EU27 and should thus be

primarily targeted by taxation measures (see section 3.1.3). However, it is crucial to consider accessibility concerns, as taxing commodities that are part of a healthy diet can have several negative impacts on consumers. More specifically, if excessive taxation is applied after harvesting, during transport and retail, the additional costs of maintaining these products in good condition could become significant. This may affect the profitability and accessibility of fresh fruit and vegetables. Additionally, the important role of inedible food waste should also be accounted for, as it makes targets more challenging to achieve (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025). By differentiating FLW reduction targets by country, actors within the FSC, and commodity type, policymakers can design more effective interventions that prioritise the most waste-intensive sectors and mitigate unintended socio-economic consequences.

Action 2: Improved FLW measurement, monitoring and frameworks

A genuine requirement for successfully achieving the intermediate targets is the improvement of FLW measurement and monitoring, alongside applying structured frameworks to ensure fairness and effectiveness. Firstly, EU policymakers should ensure that all MS are following the established EU definition of FW, as provided in the amendment to Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste, since some countries may still follow different definitions in their national strategies or plans (OECD, 2025). The EU definition provides a standardised methodology and minimum quality requirements for consistently measuring food waste levels, quantifying **both edible and inedible components** as part of the total food waste (D'haese et al., 2023). Findings from the Partial Equilibrium Model highlight the significant role of inedible food waste in achieving reduction targets, particularly the challenges posed by commodities that generate inedible FW (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025). Thus, it may be worth to review the scope of the current definition. During the roundtables, some stakeholders raised this concern, suggesting that policymakers could focus exclusively on edible waste. They argued that this approach might be more relevant given that certain types of inedible FW (e.g., chicken bones) are inherently challenging to revalorise. Thus, policymakers should consider and use this distinction to **clarify the definitions of 'avoidable' and 'unavoidable' FW** (see section 2.2.1). Some stakeholders hinted that certain types of inedible FW should be classified as 'unavoidable'.

Adopting a common definition is pivotal for ensuring consistent implementation across MS. Furthermore, **improved quantification of FLW volumes** throughout the FSC is key to achieving the proposed targets (Cattaneo et al., 2021; Section 4.2.4). As discussed in section 4.2.4, robust monitoring systems are necessary to track progress and thus meet the targets, and further investment in data infrastructure and technology is needed to guarantee data sharing and improved collaboration among stakeholders (OECD, 2025). Future regulations

should also require stakeholders to disclose waste amounts transparently, adopting a **non-punitive approach** that addresses concerns about negative publicity. The SILL1 (*F2F FLW monitoring & assessment*) has the potential to improve FLW measurement and monitoring through its data-driven platform. However, before valuable insights can be generated for policymakers, researchers, and value chain actors, data accessibility remains a key challenge – an issue further addressed in the following Just Pathway Action 3. Furthermore, established frameworks such as APEASE, EAST, and the TBL provide **structured methodologies to support monitoring efforts and policy design**, ensuring that FLW reduction measures account for social, economic, and environmental dimensions. While these frameworks are not measurement tools, they help evaluate the feasibility, effectiveness, and broader impact of interventions, guiding the development of more comprehensive and inclusive FLW reduction strategies.

Action 3: Strengthening primary production resilience

Our analysis highlighted the need for **increasing financial and technical support** for small-scale producers to improve their resilience against climate-related losses and post-harvest FW. Significant investments towards innovative technologies could have a valuable positive impact on this stage of the value chain. For example, the funding of weather-resistant agricultural techniques (e.g., drought-resistant crops, improved irrigation) and the development of post-harvest storage and transport solutions (e.g., cold chains, hermetic storage) have the potential to greatly reduce on-site FL and strengthen the producers' position in the value chain as well as the overall regional food security. As mentioned in section 3.2, there is an **urgent need** to invest and shift towards **more sustainable agricultural practices**. To fully realise these benefits, it is essential to address significant barriers faced by primary producers in accessing resources and technology. The SILLs have encountered key infrastructure and accessibility issues. **Ensuring access to innovative solutions** for the most vulnerable stakeholders aligns with the conceptual framework of a just pathway. Small farmers and businesses often lack access to necessary technology and investment resources to adopt new solutions. For instance, in Spain, small farmers have been included in relevant discussions and cooperatives often seem to play a central role in supporting outreach to small farmers and the spread of relevant innovations. **Collaborative investment models**, such as shared machines, could also help address these challenges for producers. Increasing support for cooperatives and local markets would also improve supply chain connectivity and move our food system closer to a more just transition pathway with shorter supply chains, prioritising sustainability and quality food (Drejerska and Sobczak, 2023; Section 4.2.2). SILL3 insights also highlight the need for **knowledge development** to successfully implement such innovations. In this context, cooperatives can play a crucial role in ensuring that these advancements are not limited to larger producers,

making them more accessible across the supply chain. Beyond infrastructure and financial constraints, **data accessibility** is also a critical challenge. Effective information exchange is essential for scaling up technological innovations, yet significant barriers remain. For instance, SILL1's data-driven platform could improve FLW measurement and monitoring, but obtaining the necessary data is a prerequisite. However, producers are often reluctant to share commercially sensitive data, limiting the potential for systemic improvements. This hesitation is driven by trust issues, concerns over competitive disadvantages, and asymmetries in information access – where farmers often lack the same level of data transparency as other supply chain stakeholders. Given these challenges, **horizontal peer-sharing** emerges as a key intervention to facilitate knowledge exchange and build trust among stakeholders. Based on insights from the SILLs, encouraging such data-sharing practices is crucial to ensure innovative solutions can be successfully transferred and scaled across different commodity types and context. This approach has already proven effective in some SILLs, such as SILL7 (*Efficient food banks networks*), where it helped build trust, demonstrating its potential to improve data accessibility while addressing concerns around competition and transparency.

Action 4: Subsidised waste reduction technologies

Significant large-scale public-private investments are needed to support innovation and new waste reduction technologies, unless they are groundbreaking. Thus, a just pathway that aims to meet the proposed intermediate targets must include **government-supported grants and incentives** to help businesses implement innovative waste-reduction solutions. For instance, in addition to data accessibility, SILL3 and SILL5 (*Ugly food early identification; Shelf-life assessment and alternative valorisation*), which are based on specific datasets (e.g., specific tomato variety) and tailored to specific crops or regions, require subsidies to be scaled to other commodities and systems. Furthermore, the innovations being developed in SILL2 (*Innovative Sustainable and Smart Packaging for Fresh Food Products*), SILL4 (*Mobile Food Valorisation as a service*), SILL6 (*Data-driven production process control & optimisation*) and SILL8 (*Retail Food Waste Valorisation*) also require subsidies due to high initial costs. Beyond initial costs, sustained financial support is needed, as smart packaging from SILL2 would remain more expensive than existing options even after scaling. Similarly, SILL5 highlights the high operational and maintenance costs of the innovation. As discussed in section 6.2, price remains a crucial factor for stakeholders and consumers alike, and for the adoption of these FW-reducing innovations. These challenges apply to all other SILLs, underscoring the need for **sustained financial support to drive innovation, enable scalability and ensure long-term implementation**. Direct subsidies for retailers and food processors adopting AI-driven forecasting tools could be provided, optimising purchasing. Small

restaurants could be offered low-interest loans to invest in waste-reduction technologies (e.g., portion control systems, surplus redistribution platforms). In this regard, funding for research and innovation hubs is crucial. Matching grants could be provided for food processors and farmers investing in FLW-reducing infrastructure, while funding startups and pilot projects testing new innovations. Open-access FLW data-sharing platforms can significantly aid these efforts, encouraging collaboration between public and private sectors and reducing economic barriers to FLW innovation.⁸

Furthermore, this deliverable has shown the consequences that ignoring these challenges and trade-offs can have on vulnerable consumers and businesses, especially when considering the digital divide across the FSC (Smith and Taylor, 2023; Section 4.1.4). Therefore, **ensuring equitable access to FW innovations** should be a priority for a just pathway. Cost-saving FLW innovations should be more accessible to low-income consumers and small businesses, to reduce economic disparities and strengthen the food resilience of our communities. Community-based food sharing networks that integrate digital solutions should be developed in parallel and offline access to food-sharing initiatives should be ensured for digitally excluded populations.

Innovations' adoption should always be accompanied by **vocational trainings and reskilling programs** to equip workers with skills in FW reduction and circular economy. Developing targeted training courses in food manufacturing, retail, and logistics is crucial, with potential partnerships with industry to fund apprenticeships and on-the-job training. These measures protect vulnerable workers during the transition, especially as AI-driven innovations increase automation and may lead to employment losses. A just pathway must include retraining grants or adequate compensation for affected workers. Insights from SILL5 also highlight the need for targeted investment in comprehensive staff training to ensure proper use of advanced equipment. A skilled workforce is essential to implement innovative FLW reduction technologies and meet the proposed targets, and foster job creation within a more circular food economy.

Action 5: Targeted consumer incentives

The simulations' results and the discussions in the roundtables emphasised how **consumer behaviour** should not be sidelined when devising FLW reduction policies. The complicating factor is that consumer behaviour changes slowly and is

⁸ An example discussed during the roundtables is the [NaturEaTown \(NET\) Platform](#), a blockchain-based digital solution built by the UN Economic Commission for Europe. NET empowers cities to map and track food surplus sources, addressing urban food system challenges through a tailored, virtual platform. It connects all stakeholders of the FSC, enhances local food management, and provides transparent data to improve decision-making and food redistribution policies. Platforms such as NET exemplify how technology can foster collaboration, expand access to new technologies, funding, and infrastructure.

influenced by several socio-economic factors. Nonetheless, as repeatedly emphasised by external stakeholders, true innovation should not only be technological in nature. It must also be about **social innovation** – rephrasing and changing the common perception of FW, emphasising the inherent value of food (Section 4.1.3). Encouraging social innovation should continue through **increasing awareness activities and public forums** that also increase general consumer participation in FLW reduction. However, concrete examples can further support this general direction towards a more just pathway. For instance, financial incentives for low-income households to adopt food-saving practices could make a substantial difference, considering that household FW has the largest share of total FW in the EU. This could be done via tax credits or subsidies for effective food-saving apps, discounted smart storage, or composting rebates (e.g., the Landfill Tax and Refund scheme in Catalonia). In the SILLs development, the behavioural/policy dimension is often placed outside their scope of influence. While this is often justifiable due to several constraints, it could still represent a **significant design flaw**. This is exemplified by the SILL2 innovation – the adoption of smart packaging for fresh fish, even when effectively subsidised and scaled-up, would still be dependent on consumer perception in terms of effectiveness, and affected by the current regulatory and legal system, as discussed in subsequent paragraphs. These additional dimensions must be considered, showcasing the need to accompany and align technological innovations with targeted consumer incentives, to be fully successful. Isolating technological innovations from the much relevant and connected behavioural and policy aspects represents a **considerable gap** in research and innovation, which should be addressed by future policy recommendations. SILL9 (*Informing & Nudging consumers*) is working on consumer innovations (recipes, labels) that should inform and nudge them, increasing their engagement. In the future, this scope could be extended to aid adoption of technological innovations through targeted measures (e.g., trust-building information campaigns) aimed at bridging this gap. The *Changing Practices and Habits through Open, Responsible, and Social Innovation towards Zero Food Waste* (CHORIZO) project has identified that while consumers often possess the motivation and intention to reduce FLW, the challenge lies in providing them with **practical opportunities and guidance to translate these intentions into effective actions**. The project's findings suggest that empowering consumers and creating supportive environments are crucial for enabling behaviour change (CHORIZO project, 2023). Potential incentives could include offering free waste collection for participating households by partnering with municipalities. Providing discounts on smart storage technology, such as vacuum-sealed containers or fridge sensors, could particularly help consumers address their FW. This approach promotes social

innovation and better participation, allowing individuals to feel involved in the just transition.

Action 6: Adapted regulatory and legal reforms

The SILLs identified regulatory and governance gaps highlighting the need for frameworks **aligning innovations with policy implementation**. In relation to a much-needed perception shift around FW, food redistribution and donations retain a crucial role (Rivera et al., 2023; Section 4.3.1). To encourage a cultural shift towards donation over disposal, liability laws should be reformed and clarified with the objective of reducing legal risks for donating businesses. Firstly, food safety guidelines need to be standardised and clarified, reducing ambiguity and confusion. Subsequently, mechanisms to shield food donors from potential lawsuits should be implemented, such as 'Good Samaritan-style' protections, legal safeguards that protect individuals, businesses, and organisations from liability when donating surplus food in good faith, if they comply with basic food safety regulations. Additionally, tax deductions or financial incentives could be offered to businesses donating surplus food. The impact of this focus on reforming food donations is multifunctional, ranging from significant FW reductions at the retail and food service level to the establishment and improvement of charitable food networks that will directly contribute to making our food system more just and sustainable. Insights from SILL4 and SILL7 showed that currently, food donations are not centrally coordinated, with each stakeholder managing their own donations independently.

This **fragmented approach** limits access to a diverse range of food. A centralised system would greatly improve efficiency, but the challenge lies in determining who would take on this responsibility, making it a governance issue as well. The potential of food donation reform to assist and guide this cultural shift as a fundamental feature of a just pathway should not be underestimated. Challenges identified during the study visit on Food Waste and Redistribution in Catalonia (see section 1.4.3) include the Spanish law mandating food companies to donate to redistribution organisations under contract, resulting in logistical overload. Additionally, the risk of low-quality donations increases the potential for FW generation in charities.

Other SILLs also showcased **legal and regulatory limitations**. For instance, the SILL2 smart packaging could theoretically substitute the 'best before' date. However, eventually replacing the 'use by' date in traditional labelling is problematic and politically questionable. To ensure food safety, food labelling laws strictly require a precise 'use by' date, and such innovative technologies may not be legally recognised or adjusted to fulfil all legal requirements. Furthermore, SILL4 mobile food valorisation, which was initially designed to be mobile, required authorisation at every location it intended to operate, ultimately making mobility unfeasible. The

difficulty in obtaining the necessary permits highlights a regulatory barrier and governance challenge. Hence, **addressing regulatory and governance barriers** in policy implementation is essential to unlocking the full potential of certain technological innovations.

Action 7: Inclusion of external actors and collaboration

A legal reform on food donation showcases, for instance, the central role that food banks play in food redistribution and in the development of a fairer food system. Other **external non-FSC actors** like cities and NGOs can play an equally **vital role in the transition** (see section 4.3.1). Not only do NGOs influence food policy governance and protect vulnerable groups by advocating for their rights and fighting inequalities (Moragues et al., 2017), but local governments and cities have also emerged as pioneering actors in integrating food into policy frameworks, showcasing excellent examples of FW-reducing initiatives (e.g. in schools canteens programmes) precisely because they can operate outside of the traditional production-consumption framework. **Collaboration** among policymakers, food banks, NGOs, local governments, cooperatives, FSC actors, and other key stakeholders is essential to overcoming structural challenges, as mentioned in section 4.3.2. The experience from several SILLs highlights how **partnerships** can address these challenges effectively. For example, SILL3 emphasises the importance of joint investments among farmers to improve technology access, while SILL4 showcases how mobile food valorisation efforts could benefit from stronger coordination in surplus redistribution. SILL4's assessment also highlighted that while this food valorisation innovation helps address the issue of unesthetic goods identification, it does not directly influence mindsets and perceptions of such food products. Addressing these behavioural aspects is essential for a more comprehensive approach to FW reduction. Furthermore, **horizontal peer-learning** is also a way to overcome challenges such as data sharing. EU policymakers should include external actors and promote a collaborative approach in the participatory process of the just pathway, making **strategic use** of each unique positioning in and out of the supply chain, especially in relation to regional, local initiatives.

These 'Just Pathway Actions' not only enhance the likelihood of meeting or surpassing the proposed targets but are also fundamental to improving our food system. The workshop discussions and reflections helped the ZeroW Policy Team visualise key gaps and areas where more specific policy recommendations are required, which will be produced in T8.3. Most importantly, they provided concrete **illustrative examples** of the need and urgency to implement the Just Pathway Actions identified through the simulations of the alternative policy pathways and backed by stakeholder feedback. These Just Pathway Actions play a crucial role in addressing the requirements and objectives of the *F2F Plan*, tackling the challenges

most often identified by stakeholders and partially exemplified by the simulations' results. Committing towards the achievement of the just pathway and intermediate targets requires **integrating them into policymaking** as a fundamental priority. Moreover, as shown above, the recently published OECD (2025) report 'Beyond Food Loss and Waste (FLW) Reduction Targets' offers a comprehensive overview of global FLW policy environments that provides strong evidence in favour of undertaking these 'Just Pathway Actions'. Therefore, they will also constitute the foundation for the EU Policy Briefs that the ZeroW Policy Team will produce as part of the next task of WP8 (T8.3) and will align with ongoing debates, policy developments and advocacy opportunities.

7. Conclusions

Ultimately, this report is the result of teamwork between the ZeroW Modelling Team (WP1) and the ZeroW Policy Team (WP8). Together we identified intermediate FLW reduction targets that **may be** the most just and feasible. The modelling simulations of the three alternative policy pathways serve as a **useful demonstration of the different paths** that FLW reduction can take, identifying crucial unintended consequences and effects that policymakers need to keep in mind.

The ZeroW Policy Team integrated these simulations into a conceptual framework developed to capture the complex and debatable definition of a 'just pathway' and the multiple dimensions of justice. Through analysis, interpretation, and validation of the findings in dedicated WG roundtables with stakeholders, this report serves as a practical 'policy guide' offering a well-balanced, and thoughtful **proposal for fair intermediate targets**.

The analysis found Policy Pathway 2's targets neither just nor feasible due to negative spillover effects. To align with the EC Proposal for EU-level targets for food waste reduction, we proposed a set of balanced targets combining those from Policy Pathway 1 and 3. The choice of these proposed targets goes hand in hand with the urgent need for policymakers to **carefully consider the trade-offs and their impacts on all FSC actors, especially vulnerable consumers**. Thus, the report also highlights the importance of taking specific actions to reach the proposed targets. The ZeroW Policy Team reiterates these crucial considerations to encourage reflection and directly engage policymakers. Based on the feedback from stakeholders across the FSC gathered during the roundtables, the report also highlights the potential shift in EU policymaking toward prevention and valorisation, rather than focusing solely on taxing FW disposal.

Thus, this report identifies **7 key 'Just Pathways Actions'** that policymakers should address to increase the likelihood of achieving the proposed targets and design a just pathway. Based on the insights from an internal ZeroW workshop, it integrates the progress and challenges of the innovations being developed and tested in the ZeroW SILLs. It highlights where and how SILLs innovations can support the achievement of the 'Just Pathway Actions' and intermediate targets while also signalling their key challenges. Additionally, these actions offer insights into the limitations of technological advancement and the financial viability of scaling up, thereby paving the way for more specific policy interventions. The 'Just Pathway Actions' identified and discussed in this report serve as a foundation for more evidence-based policymaking and will inform the EU Policy Briefs developed by the ZeroW Policy Team in the next phase of WP8 (T8.3). These briefs will identify areas requiring targeted policy interventions and recommendations.

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Annex I: Guiding questions for the ZeroW Food Waste roundtables

These guiding questions are meant for pre-meeting reflection and gaining familiarity with the results.

Session 1: Validation of Key Findings

1. General Feedback on Results
 - Do the findings resonate with your experience or observations in the supply chain? Why or why not?
 - Are there any critical gaps or oversights in the results presented?
2. Economic Impacts
 - What are your views on the projected economic spillovers, such as changes in land demand, wages, and production costs?
 - How do these spillovers impact your organisation or the sector you represent?
 - Are there additional economic effects that should be considered?
3. Environmental Impacts
 - Do the results on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and land use reflect the challenges faced in your region or sector?
 - Are there any overlooked environmental concerns related to FLW reduction policies?
4. Feasibility of Targets
 - Are the FLW reduction targets (e.g., 50% by 2030, 90% by 2050) feasible given current economic and technological constraints?
 - What factors might make these targets easier or harder to achieve?
5. Implementation Challenges
 - What are the main barriers to adopting the proposed policy pathways (e.g., taxes, voluntary measures)?
 - How might these barriers be addressed?

Session 2: Policy Design and Implementation Strategies

1. Policy Instrument Effectiveness
 - What are the strengths and weaknesses of taxation versus voluntary approaches in reducing FLW?

- Would a blended approach combining voluntary measures and targeted taxes be effective in your context? Why or why not?
2. Regional Considerations
 - How do the results and policy recommendations apply to specific regional contexts (e.g., high-income vs. labour-intensive agricultural regions)?
 - What modifications are needed to adapt policies to local conditions?
 3. Social Impacts
 - How can FLW policies balance environmental and economic goals with social outcomes, such as employment and affordability?
 - Are there specific groups (e.g., low-income consumers, unskilled workers) that require targeted support?
 4. Technological Innovations
 - What role do innovations (e.g., smart packaging, sustainable agricultural practices) play in achieving FLW reduction targets?
 - How can stakeholders collaborate to develop and deploy these technologies effectively?
 5. Collaboration and Partnerships
 - What are the key opportunities for collaboration among stakeholders to implement FLW policies?
 - What role should government, industry, and civil society play in supporting these policies?
 6. Long-Term Strategy
 - What steps can be taken to ensure the sustainability of FLW reduction efforts beyond 2050?
 - How should policies adapt as new technologies and market dynamics emerge?

Pre-meeting questions

These questions are meant to guide your preparation for the roundtables, allowing for optimal discussion of the feasibility and realism of the targets, as well as potential barriers and opportunities. We encourage you to answer as many as possible before the roundtables.

1. Feasibility and Effectiveness of FLW Reduction Pathways

- How feasible are the FLW reduction targets presented for 2030 and 2050 across different supply chain stages (production, processing, retail, and consumption)?

- Among the three pathways, which approach (mandatory taxes, voluntary measures, or a combination) seems most realistic to implement at scale across the EU?
- What challenges do you foresee in reaching a near-zero FLW level, particularly with high-reduction targets in Pathway 2?

2. Economic Implications for Stakeholders

- How would the expected changes in production costs and food prices impact producers, especially those in land-intensive or high-waste commodities (e.g., horticulture and cereals)?
- Are the projected changes in land demand and agricultural wages likely to affect labour dynamics, particularly for unskilled agricultural workers?
- What role should incentives or subsidies play to support producers who may face increased costs due to FLW reduction taxes?

3. Consumer Impacts and Behaviour Change

- How might changes in food prices and purchasing power influence consumer behaviour, particularly in lower-income regions within the EU?
- Could shifts in consumer demand toward plant-based commodities due to FLW reduction policies be sustained in the long term?
- What additional consumer-facing policies (e.g., awareness campaigns, waste reduction programs) might be effective alongside these pathways to enhance impact?

4. Trade and Environmental Spillovers

- What are the implications of increased food imports and reduced exports on food security and trade balance within the EU?
- How should countries with high land constraints or capital-intensive agriculture (e.g., Netherlands, Denmark) address rising land prices without compromising sustainability goals?
- What further measures could mitigate unintended environmental spillovers, such as increased GHG emissions from intensified land or fertiliser use?

5. Regional and Commodity-Specific Considerations

- How should policy approaches vary across regions with different agricultural profiles, such as labour-intensive vs. capital-intensive sectors?
- Are there specific commodities that should be prioritised in FLW reduction policies due to their larger contribution to overall FLW levels (e.g., cereals, grains, horticulture)?
- For countries with high production in animal-based products, could targeted FLW reduction incentives be balanced with broader sustainability and labour goals?

6. Policy Recommendations and Support Measures

- Do you consider the combination of voluntary and tax-based policies effective and economically feasible for stakeholders across the supply chain? Please elaborate on your answer.
- Do you think that technological innovations, such as those developed in the ZeroW project, could help in achieving near-zero FLW without placing an undue economic burden on stakeholders?
- Are there specific areas where additional policies or innovation are needed to address the spillover effects (e.g., increased fertiliser use, rising non-food emissions)?

7. Long-Term Impact and Sustainability Goals

- What long-term shifts in agricultural and consumer behaviour are necessary to sustain the benefits of near-zero FLW?
- Do the FLW reduction pathways need adaptation in light of the varying regional contexts in the EU? Please elaborate on your answer.

Annex II: List of participants for the ZeroW Food Waste roundtables

Session 1: Validation of key findings

Stakeholders attending
1. INLECOM
2. SAFE
3. Wageningen University
4. ITL
5. EUFIC
6. PROMAN Management
7. Generalitat de Catalunya
8. Too Good To Go
9. MC Sonae
10. HARVIE
11. COLDIRETTI
12. AZTI
13. VLTN
14. Copa Cogeca

Session 2: Policy design and implementation strategies

Stakeholders attending
1. SAFE
2. Wageningen University
3. ITL
4. EUFIC
5. Copa Cogeca
6. IFAPA
7. DG RTD
8. EROSKI
9. KITRO

Annex III: List of short-listed external experts and stakeholders contacted by the ZeroW Policy Team for participation in the roundtables

The two roundtables with FSC stakeholders were designed to maximise stakeholder engagement, ensuring diverse representation across all segments of the food supply chain. By actively reaching out to a broad spectrum of participants, the discussions fostered inclusive dialogue, capturing a wide range of perspectives and insights essential for validating and analysing the modelling results.

Stakeholder	Stakeholder group	Stakeholder subgroup
Andalusian Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries, Water and Rural Development. General Secretariat for Agriculture, Livestock and Food	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government
Association of Hotels and Restaurants (HOTREC)	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
AZTI Foundation	Research communities	Foundation
BEUC	Civil society & citizens	Consumer organisation
BioSense Institute	Industry & Innovators	Research centre/institute
Colruyt	Industry & Innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)
COPA-COGECA	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
EIT Food	Industry & Innovators	Innovation/tech platform
Emilia-Romagna Region - DG Agriculture	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government
Eroski	Industry & Innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)

Stakeholder	Stakeholder group	Stakeholder subgroup
Es-imperfect	Industry & Innovators	Start-ups & social business
EUCOFEL	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
EUROCOMMERCE	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
European Environmental Bureau (EEB)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
European Food Banks Federation (FEBA)	Civil society & citizens	Food bank association
European Food Information Council (EUFIC)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
EUROPEN	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
Feedback EU	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)	Institutions & policymakers	International organisation
FoodDrink Europe	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
FRESHFEL	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
<u>Fundació Espigoladors</u>	Civil society & citizens	<u>Foundation</u>
Future in our hands (Norway)	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
Good Food Good Farming	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
ITL (Institute for Transport and Logistics Foundation)	Civil society & citizens	Foundation
IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute	Research communities	Research centre/institute
Joint Research Centre (JRC)	Institutions & policymakers	EU Research Centre
DG RTD	Institutions & policymakers	EU institution

Stakeholder	Stakeholder group	Stakeholder subgroup
Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Development of Andalusia (Consejería de Agricultura, Ganadería, Pesca y Desarrollo)	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government
Multiscan Technologies SL	Industry & Innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)
Polish Zero Waste Association	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
Slow Food Europe	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
Thünen Institute (German Federal Research Institute for Rural Areas, Forestry and Fisheries)	Research communities	Research centre/institute
UCAUCE-Andalusian Consumers' Union	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
University of Bologna	Research communities	University
University of Tuscia	Research communities	University
Voedingscentrum/Netherlands Nutrition Centre	Research communities	Research centre/institute
World Resources Institute	Research communities	Research centre/institute
Zero Waste Europe	Civil society & citizens	NGO/non-profit
EUROCOOP	Industry & Innovators	Coalition/network
Tecno Alimenti	Industry & Innovators	Coalition/network
RECUPERIAMO	Industry & Innovators	Start-ups & social business
KITRO	Industry & Innovators	Start-ups & social business
GreenOvate	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
BOLTON Group	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association

Stakeholder	Stakeholder group	Stakeholder subgroup
Supermercati Il Gigante Spa	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
Coldiretti	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
ECR Loss	Industry & Innovators	Coalition/network
Carrefour	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
Mercadona	Industry & Innovators	Industry/trade association
Moreforskning Norway	Research communities	Research centre/institute
IATA-CSIC	Research communities	Research centre/institute
PROMAN Management	Research communities	Research centre/institute
Generalitat de Catalunya	Institutions & policymakers	Regional/local government
HARVIE	Industry & Innovators	Start-ups & social enterprise
MC Sonae	Industry & Innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)
Too Good to Go	Industry & Innovators	Company (production, processing, retail, waste management)

Annex IV: Internal ZeroW workshop with WP1 and WP6 - Matching exercise between D8.2 and SILLs outcomes

Just Pathway Action	SILL ⁹	Considerations
Action 1: Differentiated FLW reduction targets across countries, actors and commodities	SILL3	One-size fits all measures are ineffective due to variations in technological infrastructure - including basic resources like electricity - and challenges in dataset transferability.
Action 2: Improved FLW measurement, monitoring and frameworks	SILL1	The FLW platform can support this action, but reluctance to share essential data stems from trust issues, concerns about competitive disadvantages, and imbalances in information access among value chain actors.
Action 3: Strengthening primary production resilience	SILL1, SILL3, SILL7	Investments and knowledge development are essential. Some SILLs already operate within cooperatives, enabling joint investments, including in skill development. Cooperatives can also help prevent new technologies from becoming accessible only to larger producers while addressing workers' concerns.
Action 4: Subsidised waste reduction technologies	SILL2, SILL3, SILL4, SILL5, SILL6, SILL8 / all SILLs	These promising innovations entail significant initial and operational maintenance costs, which are not currently covered by the industry nor expected to be borne by consumers. Additionally, the behavioural changes required for adoption extend beyond the scope of these SILLs.
Action 5: Targeted consumer incentives	SILL2, SILL9	In most SILLs the technological innovation is disconnected from the behavioural aspects. These SILLs start from the behavioural angle.
Action 6: Adapted regulatory and legal reforms	SILL4, SILL7	Lack of central coordination and differing regional regulations.
Action 7: Inclusion of external actors and collaboration	SILL3, SILL4 / all SILLs	Through joint investments, stronger collaboration horizontal peer learning.

⁹ During the workshop, we matched *specific* SILLs with the Just Pathway Actions. However, the discussions revealed challenges and potential interventions that could apply to all SILLs.